

1 **Ambient air pollution and childhood obesity from infancy to late childhood: An individual**
2 **participant data meta-analysis of 10 European birth cohorts**

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85 **Abstract**

86 Ambient air pollution may contribute to childhood obesity through various mechanisms.
87 However, few longitudinal studies examined the relationship between pre- and postnatal exposure
88 to air pollution and obesity outcomes in childhood. We aimed to investigate the association
89 between pre- and postnatal exposure to air pollution and body mass index (BMI) and the risk of
90 overweight/obesity throughout childhood in European cohorts. This study included mother-child
91 pairs from 10 European birth cohorts (n=37111 (prenatal), 33860 (postnatal)). Exposure to
92 nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and fine particulate matter with aerodynamic diameter <2.5µm (PM_{2.5})
93 was estimated at the home addresses during pre- and postnatal periods (year prior outcome
94 assessment). BMI z-scores (continuous) and overweight/obesity (categorical: zBMI_{≥+2} (<5
95 years) or _{≥+1} (≥5 years) standard deviations) were derived at 0-2, 2-5, 5-9, 9-12 years.
96 Associations between air pollution exposure and zBMI were estimated separately for each
97 pollutant and cohort using linear and logistic longitudinal mixed effects models, followed by a
98 random-effects meta-analysis. The overweight/obesity prevalence ranged from 12.3-40.5%
99 between cohorts at 0-2 years, 16.7-35.3% at 2-5 years, 12.5-40.7% at 5-9 years, and 10.7-43.8%
100 at 9-12 years. Results showed no robust associations between NO₂ exposure and zBMI or
101 overweight/obesity risk. Exposure to PM_{2.5} during pregnancy was associated with 23% (95CI%
102 1.05;1.37) higher overweight/obesity risk across childhood, and higher zBMI and
103 overweight/obesity risk at 9-12 years. Heterogeneity between cohorts was considerable (I²:25-
104 89%), with some cohort-specific associations; e.g., pre- and postnatal exposure to PM_{2.5} was
105 associated with lower zBMI across age periods in UK cohorts (ALSPAC and BiB), while
106 postnatal exposure to PM_{2.5} and NO₂ was associated with higher zBMI in one Dutch cohort
107 (Generation R). Overall, this large-scale meta-analysis suggests that prenatal PM_{2.5} exposure may
108 be associated with adverse childhood obesity outcomes, but provides no evidence to support an
109 effect of postnatal air pollution exposure, although cohort-specific associations were observed.

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111 **Key-words:** Air pollution, child, pediatric obesity, urban, meta-analysis.

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1. Introduction

127 The worldwide prevalence of childhood obesity has quadrupled since the 1990s, when 65.1
128 million girls and 94.2 million boys in school-age were estimated to have obesity, with rates in
129 constant rise (Phelps et al., 2024). Obesity is a multifactorial condition and consequence of a
130 complex interaction between genes, lifestyle, social and psychological determinants (An, Ji, et
131 al., 2018; González-Muniesa et al., 2017). Overweight and obesity in early life is associated with
132 a higher risk of developing adult obesity, poorer health and lower quality of life (World Health
133 Organization, 2016), which may persist into later life if not prevented. The identification of
134 modifiable risk factors of these conditions represents an important opportunity for public health
135 interventions (World Health Organization (WHO), 2021).

136 Exposure to combustion related pollutants, such as particulate matter with aerodynamic diameter
137 $<2.5 \mu\text{m}$ ($\text{PM}_{2.5}$) $<10\mu\text{m}$ (PM_{10}), as well as nitrogen dioxide (NO_2) is widespread, with
138 approximately 56% of the population worldwide (4.4 billion people) living in more polluted,
139 urban areas (Worldbank, 2023). Long-term exposure to these pollutants, in particular to nitrogen
140 oxides (NO_x), NO_2 (Malacarne et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2021), and particulate matter ($\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and
141 PM_{10}) (Parasin et al., 2021; Zheng et al., 2024), may be associated with increased risk of
142 overweight and obesity in children, as described in four systematic reviews published in the past
143 four years. Several direct and indirect mechanisms have been proposed to explain these
144 associations, including inflammation (Jerrett et al., 2014), decreased glucose utilization in skeletal
145 muscles (Toledo-Corral et al., 2018), endocrine system disruption (Darbre, 2018), respiratory
146 diseases and decreased lung function (Wang et al., 2019), besides changes in basal metabolism
147 and appetite control of the central nervous system (McConnell et al., 2016). Indirectly, areas in
148 which motorized road traffic and air pollution levels are high, with limited safe, recreational areas
149 and/or visible smog, noise, for example, may lead to behavior changes in the population, which
150 may discourage outdoor physical activities and, consequently, increase weight gain (An, Ji, et al.,
151 2018; Tainio et al., 2021).

152 There are critical windows of exposure to air pollution, including pregnancy and birth to 1 year
153 of age, which are associated with development disorders, cancer, obesity and other conditions in
154 childhood (Spencer-Hwang et al., 2023); thus, it is possible that exposure to air pollutants during
155 these periods may also have disproportionate impacts on child growth and adiposity. However,
156 evidence is inconsistent. Prenatal exposure to ambient air pollution has been associated with fetal
157 growth restriction and low birth weight (Bekkar et al., 2020; Health Effects Institute, 2022; Hung
158 et al., 2022; Pedersen et al., 2013), decreased weight and a reduced risk of being in a trajectory
159 with accelerated body mass index (BMI) gain at the age of 4 (Fossati et al., 2020). In addition,
160 prenatal exposure has been associated with variable changes in growth rates, with increases in the
161 growth rate from the 3rd trimester of gestation up to 3 months of infancy and decreases between
162 6 months and 2 years in a study from the US (Ji et al., 2023). Others, however, did not find
163 significant associations between prenatal traffic-related air pollution exposure and childhood
164 adiposity in the first years of life (Frondelius et al., 2018; Starling et al., 2020). Regarding
165 postnatal air pollution exposure, several longitudinal and cross-sectional studies have reported
166 associations between exposure to pollutants, such as NO_2 , and higher weight in children and
167 adolescents from China (Huang et al., 2019), the Netherlands (Bloemsma et al., 2019) and Spain
168 (De Bont et al., 2019; Warkentin et al., 2023). A meta-analysis by Huang et al, using mainly
169 cross-sectional studies, indicated that postnatal exposure to ambient air pollutants, especially
170 particulate matter, was associated with increased risk of childhood obesity and weight gain
171 (Huang et al., 2022); prenatal exposure was not assessed in this meta-analysis. Others have,
172 however, reported null associations between postnatal air pollution exposure and weight
173 outcomes in childhood (Alderete et al., 2017; Fioravanti et al., 2018).

174 The heterogeneous results in the literature point to the necessity of larger studies incorporating
175 pre- and postnatal exposure windows, obesity outcomes across childhood, and different
176 geographical settings. Previous studies on air pollution and childhood obesity were mainly
177 conducted in single countries within a specific region or city and, up to now, no studies have
178 evaluated and compared associations across multiple longitudinal cohorts using individual
179 participant data. Meta-analysis of individual participant data from each trial may improve the
180 quality and scope of derived information in comparison with meta-analysis using aggregate data
181 from publications (Riley et al., 2023). Additionally, this method enables a better control over
182 confounders included in the models, as these are chosen a priori and harmonized across different
183 cohorts.

184 For these reasons, the aim of this study was to examine associations of pre- and postnatal air
185 pollution exposure with childhood sex- and age-specific measures of body mass index (BMI) and
186 overweight/obesity status, using harmonized individual participant data from 10 European birth
187 cohorts.

188 2. Material and Methods

189 2.1. Study population

190 This study was part of the European Union-funded project LifeCycle, which aims to investigate
191 the effect of diverse early life stressors on health throughout life. LifeCycle has established the
192 EU Child Cohort Network, a Europe-wide network of pregnancy and childhood cohort studies
193 with harmonized data of more than 250000 mother-child dyads. More detail on the LifeCycle
194 project and the EU Child Cohort Network can be found elsewhere (Jaddoe et al., 2020; Pinot de
195 Moira et al., 2021).

196 We analyzed data from 10 European birth cohorts. Cohorts were eligible to participate if they had
197 (i) available harmonized data on air pollution exposure estimates, (ii) harmonized data on weight
198 and height measurements in at least one age period of interest and, (iii) harmonized data uploaded
199 on a local server to undergo federated analysis through the DataSHIELD platform (Gaye et al.,
200 2014). We restricted our study population in each cohort to singletons with at least one exposure
201 estimate (pre- or postnatal) and one outcome at any age between 0 to 12 years. The following
202 cohorts were included: ABCD [Amsterdam Born Children and their Development, Amsterdam,
203 the Netherlands, period of enrolment: 2003-2004] (van Eijsden et al., 2011), ALSPAC [Avon
204 Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children, Bristol, UK, 1991–1992] (Fraser et al., 2013), BiB
205 [Born in Bradford, Bradford, UK, 2007-2011] (McEachan et al., 2024; Wright et al., 2013),
206 DNBC [Danish National Birth Cohort, Copenhagen greater area, Denmark, 1996–2002] (Olsen
207 et al., 2001), EDEN [Etude des Déterminants pré et postnatals précoces du développement et de
208 la santé de l'Enfant, Nancy and Poitiers, France, 2003-2006] (Heude et al., 2016), Gen R [the
209 Generation R Study, Rotterdam, the Netherlands, 2002–2006] (Kooijman et al., 2016), INMA
210 [Infancia y Medio Ambiente, Sabadell, Gipuzkoa, Valencia, Spain, 2003–2008] (Guxens et al.,
211 2012), MoBa [Norwegian Mother, Father and Child Cohort Study, Oslo urban area, Norway,
212 1999-2008] (Magnus et al., 2016), NINFEA [Nascita e INFanzia: gli Effetti dell'Ambiente,
213 Florence, Rome, Turin, Italy, 2005–2016] (Richiardi et al., 2007) and RHEA [RHEA Mother &
214 Child Cohort Study, Crete, Greece, 2007–2008] (Chatzi et al., 2017) (**Figure 1, Table 1**). Before
215 enrolment, all participants signed an informed consent in accordance with each center's ethics
216 committee (cohort-specific ethical approvals can be found in **Supplementary Text 1**). The
217 flowchart of cohorts and participants can be found in **Supplementary Figure 1**.

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220 **Table 1.** Summary of the cohort characteristics.

Cohort	Country	City/area	Birth years	Age range of included children ^a	Number of included children ^b	
					Prenatal	Postnatal
ABCD [Amsterdam Born Children and their Development]	the Netherlands	Amsterdam	2003-2004	0-12 years	3753 (NO ₂) 3753 (PM _{2.5})	2690 (NO ₂) 2690 (PM _{2.5})
ALSPAC [Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children]	UK	Bristol	1991-1992	0-12 years	7874 (NO ₂) 7874 (PM _{2.5})	7874 (NO ₂) 7874 (PM _{2.5})
BiB [Born in Bradford]	UK	Bradford	2007-2011	0-5 years	4029 (NO ₂) 4031 (PM _{2.5})	4006 (NO ₂) 4020 (PM _{2.5})
DNBC [Danish National Birth Cohort]	Denmark	Copenhagen greater area	1996-2002	0-2, 5-12 years	4340 (NO ₂) 4340 (PM _{2.5})	3146 (NO ₂) 3146 (PM _{2.5})
EDEN [Etude des Déterminants pré et postnatals précoces du développement et de la santé de l'Enfant]	France	Nancy and Poitiers	2003-2006	0-9 years	1186 (NO ₂) 1580 (PM _{2.5})	1185 (NO ₂) 1578 (PM _{2.5})
Gen R [the Generation R Study]	the Netherlands	Rotterdam	2002-2006	0-12 years	4345 (NO ₂) 4345 (PM _{2.5})	4334 (NO ₂) 4334 (PM _{2.5})
INMA [Infancia y Medio Ambiente]	Spain	Sabadell, Gipuzkoa, Valencia	2003-2008	0-12 years	1817 (NO ₂) 1812 (PM _{2.5})	1815 (NO ₂) 1802 (PM _{2.5})
MoBa [Norwegian Mother, Father and Child Cohort Study]	Norway	Oslo urban area	1999-2008	0-9 years	7028 (NO ₂) 7053 (PM _{2.5})	6282 (NO ₂) 6282 (PM _{2.5})
NINFEA [Nascita e INFanzia: gli Effetti dell'Ambiente]	Italy	Florence, Rome, Turin	2005-2016	0-12 years	1961 (NO ₂) 1961 (PM _{2.5})	1765 (NO ₂) 1765 (PM _{2.5})
RHEA [RHEA Mother & Child Cohort Study]	Greece	Crete	2007-2008	0-5 years	357 (NO ₂) 357 (PM _{2.5})	356 (NO ₂) 356 (PM _{2.5})

221 ^a Children with available harmonized data on air pollution exposure estimates and harmonized data on weight and
 222 height measurements in at least one age period of interest; ^b Children included in the analyses (complete cases, with no
 223 missing covariates), per cohort, by period and pollutant, with some exposure and outcome data.

224 2.2. Air pollution exposure assessment

225 The assessment of air pollution exposure was performed at the mother's residential address during
 226 pregnancy and the address at the time of each outcome assessment in each cohort. This was done
 227 in accordance with a standardized protocol for harmonized urban environment stressor data across
 228 all cohorts, developed as part of the LifeCycle project (Jaddoe et al., 2020).

229 Mean annual concentrations of NO₂ (in µg/m³) and PM_{2.5} (in µg/m³) were calculated using spatial
 230 land-use regression (LUR) models developed as part of the European Study of Cohorts for Air
 231 Pollution Effects (ESCAPE) project (Eeftens et al., 2012; Sellier et al., 2014) for cohorts where
 232 local ESCAPE models were available: ABCD, BiB, EDEN (NO₂), Gen R, INMA, MoBa (Oslo
 233 region), NINFEA and RHEA cohorts. The median LUR model variance (R²) for PM_{2.5} in ESCAPE
 234 project was 71%, with variations in different regions (e.g., Oslo, Norway – 74% and Catalunya,
 235 Spain - 86%), which was considered high to moderate, with differences due to local particularities,
 236 especially the data availability at each region. For NO₂ (EDEN) seasonalized LUR models
 237 accounted for 99% of the variance of exposure (Sellier et al., 2014). For cohorts where local
 238 ESCAPE models were not available, we used air pollution models developed as part of the Effects
 239 of Low-Level Air Pollution: A Study in Europe (ELAPSE) project (de Hoogh et al., 2018):
 240 ALSPAC, DNBC (Copenhagen greater area) and EDEN (PM_{2.5}) cohorts. In ELAPSE, LUR
 241 model variance for PM_{2.5} on all available monitoring sites explained 62% of spatial variation, and
 242 the NO₂ model on all available sites explained 59% of the spatial variation of the measured air
 243 pollution concentrations. The ESCAPE and ELAPSE models followed a very similar procedure

244 and thus were comparable. ESCAPE model was applied directly on the participants locations
245 allowing estimates at point resolution. The ELAPSE model was mapped at a $100 \times 100\text{m}$
246 resolution across Europe (de Hoogh et al., 2018).

247 To obtain estimates for each relevant exposure period in each cohort and for each participant,
248 temporal adjustment was conducted using background routine monitoring stations. Briefly, for
249 each participant the nearest routine air quality monitoring from the home address was selected
250 and daily time-series data was retrieved to fully cover the target period. The adjustment factor
251 was calculated as the ratio of the pollutant concentration from the routine monitor of each day
252 and the annual average during 2009 and 2010 (baseline years of ESCAPE and ELAPSE models,
253 respectively), following the common methodology developed within ESCAPE project (Alemany
254 et al., 2021; Ballvé et al., 2024; Cruells et al., 2024; Kogevinas et al., 2023; Pedersen et al., 2013).

255 In the LifeCycle project, average annual exposure to each pollutant was calculated for the entire
256 pregnancy period (prenatal exposure) and for every year of life, from birth up to 12 years of age.
257 For prenatal exposures, we considered whole-pregnancy exposure, not trimester-specific
258 exposures, since there are no indications in the literature for trimester specific effects (e.g.
259 (Laurent et al., 2013; Ng et al., 2017)) and since not all cohorts had available trimester-specific
260 exposure data at the time of the analysis.

261 Postnatal exposure was defined as the weighted average exposure in the year preceding the
262 outcome assessment (postnatal exposure), as in **Supplementary Text 2**.

263 *2.3. BMI and weight status outcomes*

264 We used two weight-related outcomes based on BMI: (i) continuous BMI z-scores (zBMI) and
265 (ii) categorical variables indicating weight status (normal weight (including underweight),
266 overweight/obesity). Child height (in cm), weight (in kg) and age of the offspring were either
267 measured in the clinic/research center or self-reported by parents (**Supplementary Table 1**). BMI
268 was calculated as weight (kg) divided by height squared (m^2) (Woo & Daniels, 2019), and sex-
269 and age-specific zBMI were estimated according to the World Health Organization (WHO)
270 reference curves (de Onis, 2007; WHO, 2006). zBMI values ± 5 standard deviations (SD) from
271 the population median were excluded. Weight status was defined according to the WHO as
272 follows: For children < 5 years: Normal weight (inclusive underweight) for $\text{zBMI} < +2\text{SD}$,
273 overweight for $\text{zBMI} \geq +2$ and $\text{zBMI} < +3\text{SD}$, and obesity for $\text{zBMI} \geq +3\text{SD}$ (WHO, 2006). For
274 children ≥ 5 years: Normal weight (inclusive underweight) for $\text{zBMI} < +1\text{SD}$, overweight for
275 $\text{zBMI} \geq +1$ and $\text{zBMI} < +2\text{SD}$, and obesity for $\text{zBMI} \geq +2\text{SD}$ (de Onis, 2007). We considered weight
276 status as overweight/obesity vs. normal weight. The age periods used for the outcome assessment
277 were: 0-2, 2-5, 5-9 and 9-12 years, which represent key developmental periods (infancy, pre-
278 school age, adiposity rebound, and early puberty). In cases when the child had multiple zBMI
279 measurements within an age period, the latest available measurement within the period was used.

280 *2.4. Confounders*

281 We defined confounders that were known or a plausible risk factor associated with exposure to
282 air pollution and childhood zBMI. We used Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs) to identify these
283 confounders in pre- and postnatal periods along with potential colliders that should not be adjusted
284 for (**Supplementary Figure 2**). Prenatal analyses included child sex (male/female) and exact age
285 (in months) at follow-up, maternal educational level at birth (categories described below) as an
286 indicator of individual-level socioeconomic status (SES), maternal pre-pregnancy BMI (self-
287 report or clinical measurement, in kg/m^2), maternal smoking during pregnancy (yes/no), and area-
288 level SES measured during pregnancy. In our DAGs, maternal pre-pregnancy BMI was
289 considered to be a confounder rather than a mediator, as is common in studies with a similar
290 research question (De Bont et al., 2020; Fioravanti et al., 2018; Fleisch et al., 2015, 2017;

291 Frondelius et al., 2018; Nieuwenhuijsen et al., 2019). For the postnatal analyses, we further
292 included prenatal exposure to air pollution as a confounder in the case of weak-to-moderate
293 correlation with postnatal exposure (correlation coefficient <0.8). For the multi-city cohorts
294 EDEN, INMA, and NINFEA, we further adjusted the models for city, and for ABCD, BiB, and
295 Gen R, we further included self-reported mother's ethnicity in the models (Western origin/Non-
296 western origin/Mixed). This was done based on previous findings on different levels of air
297 pollution depending on the city in the EDEN, INMA and NINFEA cohorts and the great
298 variability of ethnic origin within the study population of ABCD, BiB and Gen R cohorts, which
299 may have had an effect on zBMI outcomes in these specific populations (De Hoog et al., 2011;
300 Guxens et al., 2014; Schembari et al., 2015; West et al., 2013).

301 Two SES measures were included in this study: one individual-level (maternal education) and
302 one area-level (area deprivation index). These measures, although correlated, can capture
303 different constructs either of an individual's vulnerability to or potential for exposure to air
304 pollution (Hajat et al., 2015). Maternal education level was based on the highest ongoing or
305 completed education at the time of delivery, and was coded according to the International
306 Standard Classification of Education 97 (ISCED-97) in three categories: low (no education to
307 lower secondary; ISCED-97 categories 0-2), medium (upper and post-secondary; ISCED-97
308 categories 3-4) and high (degree and above; ISCED-97 categories 5-6) (UNESCO, 2006). An area
309 deprivation index was used as an indicator of prenatal area-level SES. This index was derived
310 from country-specific indicators categorized into tertiles, where 1 means the least deprived area
311 and 3 means most deprived area (**Supplementary Text 3**). This index was not available in MoBa.

312 As sensitivity analyses, we further included in the models two urban characteristics: a cohort-
313 specific walkability index and population density. These two measures were selected based on
314 the described association between various urban characteristics on air pollution levels and
315 childhood zBMI. Countries with higher total population exhibit higher air pollution emissions per
316 capita (with the opposite happening when looking at density in urban areas) (Castells-Quintana
317 et al., 2021). City density is also associated with increases in childhood BMI (De Bont et al.,
318 2020) and walkable cities are, on the other hand, related to lower childhood BMI (Vrijheid et al.,
319 2020), as well as lower air pollution levels (Nieuwenhuijsen, 2021). The walkability index used
320 in the current analysis included the average of the following four components capturing
321 differences in the physical environment: (i) Land use Shannon's Evenness Index (calculated as
322 the proportional abundance of each land use type multiplied by that proportion, divided by the
323 logarithm of the number of land use types within a 300 m buffer), (ii) Facility richness (calculated
324 as the number of different facility types (e.g. restaurants, shops, schools, medical centres) within
325 a 300m buffer divided by the maximum (ten) potential types (range 0 – 1), (iii) Population density
326 and (iv) Connectivity index (described as the number of street intersections within a 300m buffer)
327 with a range of 0 (less walkable) to 1 (most walkable) (Binter et al., 2022; Frank et al., 2006).
328 Each component was converted to deciles before entering to formula to have equal weight. These
329 four indices were summed and divided by four, resulting in a walkability index ranging from 0 to
330 1. Population density was expressed as the number of inhabitants per km² at the home address
331 and was calculated using the Global Human Settlement Layer (*Global Human Settlement Layer*,
332 2015) for all cohorts except MoBa for which local data were used (Robinson et al., 2018).

333 2.5. Statistical analysis

334 This study used harmonized data, which were analyzed remotely through DataSHIELD (dsBase
335 package, version 6.1.0) (Gaye et al., 2014).

336 We used a two-stage individual participant data meta-analysis approach to evaluate associations
337 between pre- and postnatal air pollution exposure and zBMI and overweight/obesity status
338 (overweight/obesity vs. normal weight). First, associations were estimated separately for each

339 cohort using linear and logistic mixed effects models with repeated measures of exposures and
340 outcomes (child id was treated as random effect and confounders as fixed effects). Then, cohort-
341 specific coefficients and standard errors were combined using random-effects meta-analysis to
342 obtain overall association estimates. Common and random effects estimates were described for
343 adjusted models; in the common effects model it is assumed that there is one true effect size
344 underlying all the studies in the meta-analysis, and in the random effects model, it is allowed that
345 true effect sizes differ from study to study (Borenstein et al., 2010). Given the heterogeneity
346 between studies in the current meta-analysis, we have focused our results on the random effects
347 estimates. All analyses were adjusted for the main confounders selected by the DAGs. Results are
348 described as beta estimates (95% confidence intervals (CI)), for zBMI for every 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ increase
349 in air pollution levels, and odds ratios (OR) (95% CI) for overweight/obesity status (*vs.* normal
350 weight). Additionally, we examined between-study heterogeneity using the I^2 statistic (%). We
351 performed longitudinal analyses on the associations on overall zBMI across all age periods and
352 stratified by age period (0-2, 2-5, 5-9 and 9-12 years). We conducted only single-pollutant
353 analysis; due to the moderate-to-very-strong correlations between pollutants (**Supplementary**
354 **Figure 3**), two-pollutant models were not performed.

355 We performed several sensitivity analyses. First, in order to assess potential effect modification
356 by sociodemographic characteristics, we repeated analyses stratifying by maternal education
357 (low/medium/high), as indicator of individual-level SES, and by residential area-level deprivation
358 index (low/medium/high) as indicator of area-level SES. Second, aiming to explore if associations
359 between air pollution exposure and child weight outcomes are independent of urban
360 characteristics, we further adjusted the models for walkability and population density (separately
361 and together in the same model). Third, to detect whether highly influential cohorts affected the
362 overall effect estimates or heterogeneity we excluded each cohort in turn using a “leave-one-out
363 analysis” approach (Viechtbauer & Cheung, 2010).

364 3. Results

365 A total of 37111 (prenatal) and 33860 (postnatal) mother-child dyads in the 10 cohort studies
366 from eight European countries were included in this study. As described in **Table 2**, mother-child
367 pairs from the BiB cohort (UK) were most likely to live in a high deprivation area (84.3%), and
368 mother-child pairs from the INMA cohort (Spain) were least likely to live in a high deprivation
369 area (12%). Child overweight/obesity status varied between cohorts and age periods, with
370 prevalence ranging between cohorts from 12.3 to 40.5% at 0-2 years, 16.7-35.3% at 2-5 years,
371 12.5-40.7% at 5-9 years, and 10.7-43.8% at 9-12 years. Full characteristics of cohorts are
372 described in **Supplementary Table 2**. Full cohort characteristics showed to be very similar to the
373 study population, with exception to maternal education, in which we see participants with lower
374 educational level in the full cohorts of NINFEA, MoBa and DNBC, compared to the study
375 population. This might be explained by the fact that the study population included mainly the
376 urban areas of each cohort, aiming to estimate urban exposures (three major Italian cities
377 (Florence, Rome, Turin) in the NINFEA cohort, Oslo urban area in the MoBa cohort, and
378 Copenhagen greater area in the DNBC cohort). Also, in the full cohort of EDEN we observe a
379 lower proportion of participants from Western origin, compared to the study population (study
380 population included the urban areas of Nancy and Poitiers). Cohort-specific information on
381 prenatal and postnatal air pollution weighted average exposure throughout the age periods, and
382 other urban exposures, are described in **Table 3**. During pregnancy, higher NO_2 and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ levels
383 were seen in the Italian cohort (NINFEA), and lower levels were seen in Greece (RHEA) and
384 Norway (MoBa), compared to the other cohorts (**Table 3**). Correlation plots between air
385 pollutants, by cohort and time of exposure (pre- and postnatal), are displayed in **Supplementary**
386 **Figure 3**.

387 Meta-analyses of the estimates from the 10 cohorts showed no evidence of an association between
388 exposure to NO₂ during pre- and postnatal periods, and zBMI and overweight/obesity across
389 childhood with overall estimates close to null (e.g., prenatal exposure to NO₂ and zBMI per
390 increment of 10µg/m³: random effects β(95%CI) 0.01(-0.01; 0.02); postnatal exposure to NO₂
391 and zBMI per increment of 10µg/m³: β(95%CI) -0.01(-0.04; 0.02) (**Figure 2**). The association of
392 pre- and postnatal NO₂ exposure with zBMI and overweight/obesity status showed considerable
393 heterogeneity between cohorts (I² range 25-74%) (**Figure 2**). Some cohort-specific associations
394 were observed: For prenatal NO₂ exposure, a positive association was observed in ABCD (zBMI
395 and overweight/obesity status) and negative, but non-significant, associations were observed for
396 ALSPAC (zBMI and overweight/obesity status). For postnatal NO₂ exposure, negative
397 associations were observed in BiB, EDEN and INMA (zBMI), ALSPAC (overweight/obesity)
398 and RHEA (zBMI and overweight/obesity). In contrast, the Dutch Gen R cohort reported a
399 positive association between postnatal NO₂ exposure with zBMI (β(95%CI) 0.04(0.02; 0.07)) and
400 overweight/obesity status (OR(95%CI) 1.14(1.02; 1.27)).

401 For prenatal PM_{2.5} exposure, increased exposure was associated with an increased risk of
402 overweight/obesity (OR(95%CI) 1.23 (1.01; 1.51), whereas a small non-significant increase in
403 zBMI was observed (β(95%CI) 0.04 (-0.03; 0.10) (**Figure 3**). There were no associations with
404 postnatal PM_{2.5} exposure. Associations for PM_{2.5} exposure also showed considerable
405 heterogeneity between cohorts, with I² values ranging from 43 to 89% (**Figure 3**). We observed
406 cohort-specific associations in both positive and negative directions: For prenatal PM_{2.5} exposure,
407 negative associations were found for ALSPAC (zBMI), and positive associations were seen for
408 Gen R (zBMI and overweight/obesity). For postnatal PM_{2.5} exposure, negative associations were
409 seen in ALSPAC, INMA and RHEA (zBMI and overweight/obesity), BiB (zBMI, only) and
410 positive associations were seen for Gen R (zBMI and overweight/obesity).

411 **Figure 4** shows results of the meta-analyses stratified by age period of the outcome assessment.
412 Associations between air pollution exposures and zBMI and overweight/obesity status were close
413 to null in most age periods and did not reach statistical significance. In the period between 9-12
414 years, higher exposure to PM_{2.5} during pregnancy was associated with a statistically significant
415 increase in zBMI per increments of 10µg/m³ (β(95%CI) 0.13(0.03; 0.24) and in the risk of
416 overweight/obesity (OR(95%CI) 1.29(1.04; 1.60)).

417 Analyses stratified by individual- and area-level SES showed little difference in associations by
418 SES, with overlapping confidence intervals between the SES strata. Nevertheless, in the most
419 deprived area-level SES group (T3) a statistically significant association was observed between
420 prenatal PM_{2.5} and increased zBMI per increments of 10µg/m³ (β(95%CI) 0.10(0.01; 0.18)). A
421 weaker positive association was found between prenatal NO₂ exposure and zBMI per increments
422 of 10µg/m³ in this SES group (β(95%CI) 0.03(0.00; 0.06)) (**Supplementary Figures 4 and 5**).
423 Some negative associations in specific SES groups were seen in the postnatal exposure period
424 (e.g., in the medium deprivation group of area-level SES for postnatal PM_{2.5} exposure and zBMI
425 per increments of 10µg/m³ (β(95%CI) -0.19(-0.34 to -0.04)).

426 Models with further adjustments by walkability and population density showed similar effect
427 estimates to our main models without these adjustments (**Supplementary Figure 6**). Sensitivity
428 analyses excluding one cohort at the time mostly showed minor changes in β and OR estimates
429 that do not change the main conclusions. An exception was the association between prenatal NO₂
430 and overweight/obesity risk which increased from 1.01 (95%CI 0.96; 1.07) (overall random-effect
431 OR) to 1.28 (95%CI 1.04;1.58) when removing the DNBC cohort. Decreases in the heterogeneity
432 (I²) were observed mainly for prenatal NO₂ exposure, especially when removing the ABCD
433 cohort, and for prenatal PM_{2.5} exposure, especially when removing the Generation R cohort.
434 (**Supplementary Tables 3 and 4**).

Table 2. Study population characteristics - outcomes and covariates.

	ABCD	ALSPAC	BiB	DNBC	EDEN	Gen R	INMA	MoBa	NINFEA	RHEA
Total N										
Prenatal	3753		4029 (NO ₂), 4031 (PM _{2.5})	4340	1186 (NO ₂), 1580 (PM _{2.5})	4345	1817 (NO ₂), 1812 (PM _{2.5})	7028 (NO ₂), 7053 (PM _{2.5})	1961	357
Postnatal	2690	7874	4006 (NO ₂), 4020 (PM _{2.5})	3146	1185 (NO ₂), 1578 (PM _{2.5})	4334	1815 (NO ₂), 1802 (PM _{2.5})	6282	1765	356
Area-level deprivation^a - n (%)										
Low	1178 (22.34)	2711 (29.98)	302 (3.05)	3459 (54.46)	654 (38.88)	1302 (15.22)	939 (48.25)	-	774 (39.25)	161 (42.04)
Medium	571 (10.83)	3107 (34.35)	1255 (12.69)	1576 (24.81)	429 (25.51)	1786 (20.87)	773 (39.72)	-	662 (33.57)	122 (31.85)
High	3524 (66.83)	3226 (35.67)	8336 (84.26)	1316 (20.72)	599 (35.61)	5469 (63.91)	234 (12.02)	-	536 (27.18)	100 (26.11)
Missing	341 (6.07)	33 (0.36)	5 (0.05)	1863 (22.68)	40 (2.32)	72 (0.83)	6 (0.31)		481 (19.61)	515 (57.35)
Maternal education at birth - n (%)										
High	2909 (52.22)	1235 (14.46)	2528 (27.73)	4174 (68.63)	957 (55.87)	3473 (45.2)	668 (34.96)	7486 (85.71)	1665 (69.78)	283 (31.55)
Medium	1512 (27.14)	5906 (69.16)	1416 (15.53)	1070 (17.59)	656 (38.3)	3420 (44.51)	784 (41.03)	1169 (13.38)	641 (26.87)	458 (51.06)
Low	1150 (20.64)	1399 (16.38)	5174 (56.74)	838 (13.78)	100 (5.84)	790 (10.28)	459 (24.02)	79 (0.9)	80 (3.35)	156 (17.39)
Missing	43 (0.77)	537 (5.92)	780 (7.88)	2132 (25.96)	9 (0.52)	946 (10.96)	41 (2.1)	582 (6.25)	67 (2.73)	1 (0.11)
Maternal pre-pregnancy BMI (kg/m²)^b - Median (P5, P95)	22.2 (18.59, 30.85)	-	27.73 (20.57, 33.51)	21.72 (18.41, 28.71)	22.1 (18.14, 31.99)	22.66 (18.69, 32.35)	22.53 (18.68, 31.9)	-	21.34 (17.92, 29.06)	23.51 (18.81, 34.59)
Missing	433 (7.71)	7874 (100.0)	5537 (55.94)	559 (6.81)	33 (1.92)	2088 (24.2)	18 (0.92)	9316 (100)	41 (1.67)	6 (0.67)
Maternal smoking during pregnancy - n(%)										
Yes	617 (10.99)	2024 (25.0)	1588 (16.07)	2083 (25.6)	433 (25.22)	1910 (25.95)	605 (31.43)	1561 (16.76)	196 (8.08)	283 (33.41)
Missing	2 (0.04)	980 (10.8)	19 (0.19)	76 (0.93)	5 (0.29)	1270 (14.72)	27 (1.38)	1 (0.01)	26 (1.06)	51 (5.68)
Maternal ethnicity										
Western origin	3193 (57.26)	8329 (98.38)	4130 (41.7)	-	1474 (85.6)	4643 (56.98)	1829 (95.51)	-	-	891 (99.66)
Non-western origin	1650 (29.59)	137 (1.62)	5571 (56.3)	-	8 (0.47)	2704 (33.19)	86 (4.49)	-	-	3 (0.34)
Mixed	733 (13.15)	0 (0)	185 (1.87)	-	6 (0.35)	801 (9.83)	0 (0)	-	-	0 (0)
Missing	38 (0.68)	611 (6.73)	12 (0.12)	8214 (100)	234 (13.6)	481 (5.57)	37 (1.90)	9316 (100)	2453 (100)	4 (0.45)
Child sex - n (%)										
Male	2787 (49.64)	4579 (50.45)	5094 (51.46)	4194 (51.06)	898 (52.15)	4350 (50.41)	1006 (51.54)	4727 (50.74)	1264 (51.53)	478 (53.23)
Child age (months) - Median (P5, P95)										
0-2 years	14 (12, 20)	12 (12, 12)	0 (0, 23)	12 (12, 14)	12 (0, 15)	14 (4, 19)	14 (12, 18)	12 (1, 16)	12 (3, 18)	14 (2, 20)

2-5 years	44 (26, 54)	49 (31, 49)	51 (25, 59)	-	48 (35, 57)	37 (24, 47)	51 (48, 55)	36 (24, 36)	48 (48, 48)	49 (48, 57)
5-9 years	69 (61, 85)	99 (69, 103)	-	85 (79, 88)	66 (60, 70)	72 (68, 89)	93 (75, 106)	84 (60, 84)	84 (75.35, 93)	-
9-12 years	128 (120, 141)	140 (127, 141)	-	133 (130, 138)	-	116 (113, 122)	131 (111, 140)	-	122 (119, 129)	-
Child zBMI^c - Median (P5, P95)										
0-2 years	0.48 (-1.14, 2.04)	0.79 (-0.68, 2.29)	-0.37 (-2.31, 1.57)	0.3 (-1.47, 2.12)	0.36 (-1.57, 1.94)	0.55 (-1.15, 2.08)	0.42 (-1.2, 2.03)	0.25 (-1.32, 1.82)	0.05 (-2.11, 2.12)	0 (-1.77, 1.77)
2-5 years	0.27 (-1.26, 1.95)	0.61 (-0.84, 2.17)	0.46 (-1.18, 2.44)	-	0.14 (-1.37, 1.66)	0.37 (-1.19, 2.06)	0.51 (-0.95, 2.45)	0.43 (-1.31, 2.1)	0.08 (-1.85, 2.06)	0.59 (-1.07, 2.81)
5-9 years	0.11 (-1.34, 1.97)	0.24 (-1.56, 2.42)	-	-0.06 (-1.61, 1.51)	-0.01 (-1.39, 1.52)	0.36 (-1.04, 2.29)	0.71 (-1.03, 2.9)	-0.02 (-1.74, 1.67)	-0.02 (-1.9, 2.09)	-
9-12 years	0.02 (-1.66, 2.16)	0.36 (-1.52, 2.4)	-	-0.28 (-1.97, 1.42)	-	0.29 (-1.3, 2.31)	0.76 (-1.29, 2.71)	-	0.07 (-2.23, 1.91)	-
Child overweight/obesity status^c - yes, n (%)										
0-2 years	1357 (28.7)	477 (40.49)	1003 (12.33)	1122 (25.1)	418 (25.32)	2107 (31.08)	510 (26.32)	1797 (20.96)	444 (21.38)	147 (17.21)
2-5 years	1014 (22.05)	358 (32.05)	2315 (29.96)	-	254 (16.67)	1646 (25.5)	502 (30.91)	1577 (28.4)	374 (19.63)	281 (35.26)
5-9 years	782 (18.57)	2111 (25.66)	-	644 (12.49)	162 (13.81)	1709 (25.58)	581 (40.74)	1072 (15.38)	247 (21.15)	-
9-12 years	726 (22.39)	2504 (31.7)	-	463 (10.65)	-	1466 (26.39)	412 (43.83)	-	95 (20.08)	-

436 ABCD: Amsterdam Born Children and their Development; ALSPAC: Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children; BiB: Born in Bradford; DNBC: Danish National Birth Cohort; EDEN: Etude
437 des Déterminants pré et postnatals précoces du développement et de la santé de l'Enfant; Gen R: Generation R Study; INMA: Infancia y Medio Ambiente; MoBa: Norwegian Mother, Father and Child
438 Cohort Study; NINFEA: Nascita e INFanzia: gli Effetti dell'Ambiente; RHEA: Rhea Mother & Child Cohort Study; P: Percentile; BMI: Body mass index, zBMI: Body mass index z-score.^a Area-level
439 deprivation defined in each cohort, as described in Supplementary Text 3; ^b Maternal pre-pregnancy BMI defined as weight/height²; ^c Sex- and age- specific zBMI and child weight status were estimated
440 according to the World Health Organization (WHO) reference curves (de Onis, 2007; WHO, 2006).

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Table 3. Study population characteristics – prenatal and postnatal air pollution estimates^a and other urban characteristics.

	ABCD	ALSPAC	BiB	DNBC	EDEN	Gen R	INMA	MoBa	NINFEA	RHEA
Total N										
Prenatal	3753	7874	4029 (NO ₂), 4031 (PM _{2.5})	4340	1186 (NO ₂), 1580 (PM _{2.5})	4345	1817 (NO ₂), 1812 (PM _{2.5})	7028 (NO ₂), 7053 (PM _{2.5})	1961	357
Postnatal	2690		4006 (NO ₂), 4020 (PM _{2.5})	3146	1185 (NO ₂), 1578 (PM _{2.5})	4334	1815 (NO ₂), 1802 (PM _{2.5})	6282	1765	356
Prenatal air pollution exposure (µg/m³)^b - Median (P5, P95)										
NO ₂	36.62 (27.53, 48.16)	27.21 (19.22, 33.38)	23.04 (18.16, 29.98)	47.27 (38.72, 57.91)	21.28 (11.3, 48.92)	38.35 (30.41, 49.36)	26.23 (10.13, 51.65)	20.66 (10.87, 37.17)	49.25 (19.49, 76.25)	11.39 (7.9, 21.89)
Missing	118 (2.1)	193 (2.13)	15 (0.15)	634 (7.72)	464 (27)	37 (0.43)	108 (5.53)	962 (10.33)	352 (14.35)	1 (0.11)
PM _{2.5}	18.47 (16.78, 21.02)	13.33 (11.92, 14.67)	10.43 (8.62, 12.66)	18.22 (14.89, 20.9)	17.11 (14.17, 21.1)	19.62 (16.88, 23.82)	14.72 (10.89, 18.89)	10.8 (7.73, 14.46)	24.39 (9.64, 35.71)	14.18 (11.02, 18.67)
Missing	118 (2.1)	193 (2.13)	5 (0.05)	634 (7.72)	2 (0.12)	37 (0.43)	114 (5.84)	937 (10.06)	352 (14.35)	1 (0.11)
Postnatal NO₂ - weighted average										
0-2 years	35.01 (26.67, 45.04)	27.18 (19.69, 33.11)	24.21 (18.76, 34.79)	45.12 (37.14, 53.34)	20.57 (11.06, 46.91)	37.36 (30.29, 47.23)	27.53 (9.54, 50.79)	35.16 (24.62; 44.15)	48.67 (18.04, 75.18)	13.65 (10.59, 24.8)
2-5 years	34.32 (26.27, 43.86)	27.09 (19.72, 32.76)	25.94 (13.71, 33.54)	-	17.92 (10.48, 39.5)	35.08 (27.94, 43.68)	22.25 (8.54, 46.68)	35.19 (24.4, 45.44)	45.41 (16.99, 61.07)	13.92 (10.71, 25.03)
5-9 years	32.09 (25.01, 41.43)	23.57 (16.17, 29.57)	-	40.28 (32.12, 50.9)	15.99 (10.12, 33.73)	32.9 (24.08, 41.05)	22.75 (8.15, 46.85)	33.28 (23.27, 44.47)	44.15 (19.98, 59.05)	-
9-12 years	15.24 (11.15, 32.29)	22.08 (15.17, 26.9)	-	33.39 (26.78, 39.8)	-	29.03 (17.8, 36.67)	26.8 (3.04, 43.76)	-	40.99 (22.61, 51.48)	-
Postnatal PM_{2.5} - weighted average										
0-2 years	17.56 (16.69, 19.48)	13.37 (12.18, 14.41)	10.7 (8.9, 14.75)	18.44 (15.19, 21.04)	16.67 (14.25, 18.93)	17.99 (16.96, 22.78)	14.89 (10.72, 18.72)	9.84 (6.80; 13.7)	24.44 (8.68, 36.61)	17.29 (14.95, 20.23)
2-5 years	17.71 (16.81, 19.34)	13.39 (12.23, 14.48)	11.87 (6.12, 14.1)	-	15.86 (13.5, 18.39)	17.49 (16.31, 19.28)	13.31 (10.53, 15.72)	9.14 (6.45; 12.1)	22.77 (8.32, 26.92)	17.83 (15.37, 20.69)
5-9 years	17.02 (16.22, 18.37)	11.62 (10.22, 13.59)	-	16.07 (13.12, 19.37)	15.37 (13.44, 17.81)	16.18 (15.53, 17.38)	13.69 (10.61, 15.85)	7.66 (5.67; 10.57)	21.74 (12.15, 26.76)	-
9-12 years	7.42 (7.01, 15.3)	11.04 (9.8, 11.99)	-	14.34 (11.93, 16.58)	-	14.94 (12.9, 17.42)	12.65 (9.16, 14.65)	-	20.13 (14.4, 22.84)	-

Population density during pregnancy (persons/km² in 100m) - Median (P5, P95)	6752.25 (3132.1, 6842.3)	4320 (775.45, 11616)	5552 (1225.04, 19312)	8233.43 (2047.07, 19800.6)	2092.98 (114.51, 7595.57)	4136.41 (2457.38, 4136.41)	6121.41 (608.85, 12049.58)	6412.18 (1934.02, 25572.41)	10202.16 (5321.16, 10202.16)	5458.87 (333.25, 6887.29)
Walkability during pregnancy (0-1 range; 300m buffer) - Median (P5, P95)	0.38 (0.25, 0.48)	0.28 (0.2, 0.42)	0.32 (0.22, 0.45)	0.38 (0.25, 0.55)	0.28 (0.2, 0.4)	0.35 (0.28, 0.45)	0.32 (0.22, 0.48)	0.3 (0.17, 0.45)	0.38 (0.3, 0.48)	0.38 (0.2, 0.5)
<i>Missing</i>	126 (2.24)	210 (2.31)	49 (0.5)	503 (6.12)	147 (8.54)	952 (11.03)	165 (8.45)	1038 (11.14)	363 (14.8)	19 (2.12)
<i>Missing</i>	115 (2.05)	301 (3.32)	9 (0.09)	503 (6.12)	404 (23.46)	957 (11.09)	133 (6.81)	2224 (23.87)	353 (14.39)	237 (26.39)

447 ABCD: Amsterdam Born Children and their Development; ALSPAC: Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children; BiB: Born in Bradford; DNBC: Danish National Birth Cohort; EDEN:
448 Etude des Déterminants pré et postnataux précoces du développement et de la santé de l'Enfant; Gen R: Generation R Study; INMA: Infancia y Medio Ambiente; MoBa: Norwegian Mother, Father
449 and Child Cohort Study; NINFEA: Nascita e INFanzia: gli Effetti dell'Ambiente; RHEA: Rhea Mother & Child Cohort Study; P: Percentile. ^aValues are described as weighted average air pollution
450 levels in the different age periods; ^b Ambient air pollution levels were estimated using land-use regression (LUR) models developed within the European Study of Cohorts for Air Pollution Effects
451 (ESCAPE) project (Eeftens et al., 2012) and through the Effects of Low-Level Air Pollution: A Study in Europe (ELAPSE) project (de Hoogh et al., 2018).

452 **4. Discussion**

453 In this meta-analysis of individual participant data from 10 European cohorts and a sample size of
454 37111 (prenatal) and 33860 (postnatal) mother-child pairs, pre- and postnatal exposure to NO₂ and
455 PM_{2.5} showed few associations with obesity-related outcomes across key developmental periods during
456 childhood. Exposure to PM_{2.5} during pregnancy was associated with higher overweight/obesity risk
457 across childhood, and specifically with higher zBMI and overweight/obesity risk in one age period (9-
458 12 years). Considerable heterogeneity between cohorts was noted, with some cohorts showing
459 increased zBMI or overweight/obesity risk with increased air pollution exposure, and others showing
460 negative or null associations.

461 This study investigated both pre- and postnatal ambient air pollution exposure and obesity-related
462 outcomes during childhood in a multi-cohort study using individual participant data, rather than
463 aggregate estimates from publications. Associations between pre- and postnatal air pollution exposures
464 and childhood obesity-related outcomes have been studied in a number of single cohort studies, but
465 results are inconsistent. Regarding prenatal air pollution exposure, various studies have shown that
466 exposure to pollutants during pregnancy, such as PM_{2.5}, may be associated with decreased weight and
467 BMI at birth and in first years of life (Bekkar et al., 2020; Fossati et al., 2020; Hung et al., 2022). Two
468 studies in the US suggested a complicated and dynamic exposure-weight relationship between the
469 exposure to air pollution in prenatal life and weight outcomes. Infants in the Project Viva cohort
470 exposed to higher prenatal traffic-related air pollution (PM_{2.5} and black carbon) exhibited reduced fetal
471 growth at birth and rapid postnatal weight-for-length gain between 0-6 months of age (Fleisch et al.,
472 2015). More recently, Ji and colleagues found that those children exposed to higher levels of NO₂ had
473 faster “catch-up growth” rates in early infancy, which may lead to increased risk of obesity later in life
474 (Ji et al., 2023). However, other studies that investigated maternal prenatal particulate matter exposure
475 and child weight-related outcomes, did not show significant associations with childhood BMI (Huang
476 et al., 2019; Sears et al., 2019), cardiometabolic health (Fleisch et al., 2017) nor BMI trajectories
477 (Fleisch et al., 2019). In the current study, we observed an association between prenatal PM_{2.5} exposure
478 and greater overweight/obesity risk across childhood, and specifically with higher zBMI and
479 overweight/obesity risk in one age period (9-12 years). However, this age-specific analysis was based
480 on less cohorts than the repeated outcome analysis due to less cohorts having data in this age group,
481 and this result needs to be interpreted with caution. Experimental studies in animals have shown that
482 PM_{2.5} exposure during pregnancy led to decreased body and tail length, birth weight, and survival rates
483 of the young mice (Huang et al., 2023), the development of increased body weight, altered blood
484 pressure, and increased susceptibility to cardiovascular disease and heart failure in offspring's
485 adulthood (Weldy et al., 2014), besides increased risk for metabolic syndrome in the offspring (Zhang
486 et al., 2019). Further studies are necessary to better understand how prenatal air pollution exposure
487 may affect adiposity-related outcomes in different key developmental periods during childhood.

488 We found no evidence for an association between postnatal air pollution exposure and childhood zBMI
489 and overweight/obesity status. The literature has also been inconsistent with respect to findings on the
490 association between postnatal air pollution exposure and weight outcomes in childhood. In China,
491 exposure to PM₁, PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀ and NO₂ was associated with increased zBMI, waist circumference and
492 waist-to-height ratio, and higher prevalence of both general and central obesity, in children and
493 adolescents (Zhang et al., 2021). In a recent natural experiment study in Catalonia, Spain, those
494 children and adolescents who moved to more polluted areas (NO₂, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}) showed
495 prospective increases in zBMI (Warkentin et al., 2023). The study by De Bont and colleagues, also in
496 Catalonia, highlighted that ambient air pollution exposure in childhood, especially at school, was
497 associated with 30% increased odds of having overweight or obesity (De Bont et al., 2019). Another
498 study, using the PIAMA birth cohort in the Netherlands, showed that NO₂ exposure throughout
499 childhood was associated with an increased odds (adjusted OR=1.40) of overweight in children aged
500 3-17 years (Bloemasma et al., 2019). However, others reported null findings. A study in Italy did not

501 find a significant association between long-term exposure to air pollution (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO₂, NO_x,
502 coarse particles, and PM_{2.5abs}) and traffic density, and several body weight measures including BMI,
503 waist circumference, waist-to-height ratio and prevalence of overweight/obesity in 4-8-year-olds
504 (Fioravanti et al., 2018). In another study in the south of the UK, PM₁₀ exposure in preschool-age (4-
505 5 years) was associated with small relative risk of overweight/obesity at 10 years, however not the
506 other pollutants (PM_{2.5}, NO_x) (Wilding et al., 2020). A recent systematic review concluded that there
507 is strong evidence of association between NO₂ and NO_x (which are traffic-related pollutants) and
508 childhood obesity, but evidence is still weak for PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} (which are driven to a lesser degree
509 by local traffic). It is argued that the biochemical mechanisms in which NO₂ is involved in the human
510 body might also impact the onset of obesity (Malacarne et al., 2022). Besides variability of associations
511 between air pollution and weight by specific air pollutants, this link may also vary by sex, age group
512 (children vs. adults) (An, Ji, et al., 2018), study design (cross-sectional vs. longitudinal),
513 methodological disparities in body weight and air pollution measurements, and heterogeneity of study
514 populations (Zhang et al., 2021).

515 Our study finds prenatal, but not postnatal, exposure to PM_{2.5} to be associated with obesity-related
516 outcomes in childhood. From the previous epidemiological studies, described above, there is no clear
517 indication of which time window of exposure would be expected to be more sensitive for the
518 development of childhood obesity. Our study results, if causal, support evidence for mechanisms
519 during pregnancy, rather than during childhood, to be of most concern. Further studies into the critical
520 time windows for the potential effects of air pollution on childhood obesity are needed to support this.
521 Our study also suggests that prenatal PM_{2.5}, but not NO₂, exposure is associated with obesity-related
522 outcomes in children. Previous studies do not provide clear evidence on whether PM_{2.5} may be more
523 likely to be associated with obesity than NO₂. We note that NO₂ and PM_{2.5} share common sources and
524 are mainly driven by combustion-related activities, such as vehicle exhaust and agricultural emissions
525 (Cai et al., 2020). Differences between the pollutants include that NO₂ has been described to be a more
526 local, short-lived trace gas (Matandirotya & Burger, 2021), whereas PM_{2.5} can be transported over
527 regional and long-range transboundary distances (Jun & Gu, 2023). Our study included mainly urban
528 areas and traffic would be the main source of both pollutants in these study areas. The two pollutants
529 showed moderate to strong correlations in the current study, and differences in study areas can partly
530 explain differences in correlations between cohorts.

531 Possible explanations for the inconsistencies and heterogeneity between cohorts found in the
532 association between air pollution exposure, both during pregnancy and in childhood, and childhood
533 BMI may reflect a number of factors including: (i) different levels of air pollution exposure in the
534 different cohorts; (ii) possible differences in lifestyle behaviors of children from different countries,
535 which may alter their exposure to ambient air pollution and have an effect on weight; and (iii) possible
536 residual confounding by SES and other factors specific to each city environment. Residual
537 confounding may, for example, explain the association between higher air pollution levels and lower
538 BMI we observed in the British BiB cohort. This cohort is characterized by a high level of
539 socioeconomic deprivation and ethnic diversity, with half of the sample of Pakistani origin, a
540 population that lives in the most polluted and deprived parts of the city, whilst at the same time having
541 a lower BMI (West et al., 2018) and lower susceptibility to air pollution exposure for some outcomes,
542 such as birth weight, compared to their White British peers (Schembari et al., 2015). Our adjustment
543 for ethnicity and SES may not have completely controlled for these effects. Also, we note that the
544 cohorts studied were very socially diverse, and that the relationship between SES and air pollution
545 exposure can vary between cities, with some low SES communities facing higher exposure to air
546 pollution and other environmental hazards and others lower exposures (Hajat et al., 2015; Robinson et
547 al., 2018). In the Spanish cohort INMA, for example, contrasting patterns were seen among cities, with
548 highly educated families being exposed to higher levels of air pollution in Sabadell, and the opposite
549 pattern in Valencia. In Oslo (MoBa), however, high income families were exposed to higher levels of
550 NO₂ and in Bradford (BiB) the opposite was found (i.e., high family education and high family income

551 were exposed to lower levels of air pollutants) (Robinson et al., 2018). To summarize, these are some
552 examples of factors that might explain the high heterogeneity found in the current study and the
553 complex and dynamic relation between air pollution exposure and childhood weight.

554 The major strength of this study is the large geographical coverage including eight countries and 10
555 cohorts in Europe, which enabled the study of culturally diverse populations. We were also able to
556 include different urban environments, besides urban characteristics that could be confounders in our
557 analyses. Additionally, we meta-analyzed individual participant data from different cohorts, which
558 may have improved the quality and scope of derived information (Riley et al., 2023), increased our
559 statistical power and enabled more precise estimates compared to single cohort studies. Finally, one
560 important practicality of the current study is the use of federated analyses, which enabled the analysis
561 of data from multiple studies/cohorts without the need of data transfer, decreasing the administrative
562 burden of data transfer agreements, and governance issues of physical data sharing (Cadman et al.,
563 2023).

564 This study also has limitations that need to be mentioned. First, two different spatial models (ESCAPE
565 and ELAPSE) were used to estimate the exposures. Although they were developed using sampling
566 data from the same period and a common methodology, some differences might occur. Model year
567 development (2009-2010) may be seen as a limitation to represent a scenario several years later than
568 the pregnancy exposure time period and earlier than the childhood exposure periods. However, for
569 most of our cohorts, exposure estimation and health outcome data collection fell within a time period
570 of 10 years either side of the spatial modelling and many predictor variables in LUR models (such as
571 building density, green spaces, distance to roads, etc.) have shown to be stable over time (Beelen et
572 al., 2007; Eeftens et al., 2011; Gulliver et al., 2013; Johnson et al., 2010). Besides, stability of the
573 spatial structure of the ESCAPE and ELAPSE models was confirmed and agreement in spatial
574 variation was reported to be generally high in Europe (de Hoogh et al., 2018). One outlier is the
575 ALSPAC cohort with years of birth in 1991-1992 and a 12-year follow-up included in this study
576 leading to longer term back-extrapolation of the spatial models. Our sensitivity analysis leaving this
577 cohort out showed that main conclusions remain the same. Secondly, missing data were addressed
578 using complete cases, as imputation methods were not available within DataSHIELD at the time of the
579 study. We recognize that missing data on covariates might introduce bias into our findings, and
580 determining the direction of this bias presents a challenge. Aiming to explore if any of the cohorts with
581 more missings (such as cohort BiB and cohort DNBC) could have had an effect on the overall pooled
582 estimate, we performed sensitivity analyses using the “leave-one-out” approach, which showed no
583 meaningful cohort-specific effect on the pooled estimates in the majority of cohorts, except when
584 excluding the DNBC cohort. The observed changes in pooled estimates when excluding DNBC cohort
585 might be explained by the fact that this cohort showed higher proportion of missing values, in variables
586 such as area-level SES (22.7%) and maternal education (26%), compared to the other cohorts, and no
587 zBMI data on the age-group 2-5 years. Besides, DNBC is one of the biggest cohorts included in our
588 analyses, so with higher weight in our analysis compared to smaller sample size cohorts. As discussed
589 previously, considerable heterogeneity was found in this study with included cohorts, which might
590 explain the changes in the “leave-one-out” analysis. Third, the use of different cohorts includes
591 harmonization challenges, with variables being harmonized in different ways and in different levels of
592 detail, which may have resulted in between-study heterogeneity that could affect the interpretation of
593 results. More specifically, not all cohorts had data covering all age periods by the end date of data
594 inclusion of this study (e.g., BiB, EDEN and MoBa). Also, not all cohorts had objectively measured
595 anthropometric data (as described in **Supplementary Table 2**), so we had to rely on parent-reported
596 information for some cohorts (e.g., DNBC, MoBa and NINFEA). In addition, we had to harmonize
597 variables with the least detail, which could have increased the risk of residual confounding leading to
598 greater heterogeneity of estimates. For example, maternal education was harmonized in three
599 categories from more granular detail variables within many of the cohorts. Similarly, maternal
600 smoking during pregnancy was used as a yes/no answer in the current study, however was asked in

601 more detail in several cohorts (which included, for example, the number of cigarettes and the timing
602 of smoking). Fourth, although models were adjusted for both individual-level and area-level SES
603 indicators, we cannot rule out the possibility of bias in our effect estimates due to residual confounding
604 of SES. Also, regarding SES, we used as a proxy of individual-level SES maternal education, which
605 is commonly used in epidemiological studies (Hajat et al., 2015), since household income was not
606 available in all included cohorts. Fifth, we were not able to take into account other personal and
607 environmental factors that may influence pediatric obesity, such as physical activity and noise levels
608 (An, Zhang, et al., 2018; González-Muniesa et al., 2017; Jebeile et al., 2022; Wu et al., 2017) due to
609 high missingness and absence of harmonized variables for these factors. We therefore took advantage
610 of availability of family characteristics (e.g., maternal education, BMI, smoking, SES) which influence
611 childhood weight outcomes (Jebeile et al., 2022), along with alternative urban environment features,
612 such as walkability and population density, which may be seen as noise sources due to human activities
613 emission in the neighborhood (Yuan et al., 2019). Lastly, both indoor and outdoor air pollution may
614 have important health effects in the population. Since we did not have data on indoor air pollution, we
615 relied on data of outdoor air pollution only. It is worth noting that a considerable proportion of indoor
616 air pollution comes from outdoors (Amato et al., 2014). Future studies should take into account both
617 indoor and outdoor air pollution exposures, especially in indoor places where children spend a lot of
618 time, such as schools (De Bont et al., 2019), aiming to increase robustness of estimates.

619 **5. Conclusions**

620 In conclusion, this large-scale meta-analysis suggest that prenatal PM_{2.5} exposure may be associated
621 with adverse childhood obesity outcomes, but provides little evidence to support an effect of postnatal
622 air pollution exposure although cohort-specific associations were observed.

623

624 **Funding**

625 The LifeCycle project received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and
626 innovation programme (Grant Agreement No. 733206 LifeCycle). This project has also received
627 funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant
628 agreement No 874583 (ATHLETE project) and No 874739 (LongITools project).

629 **ABCD:** Core funding of the ABCD-study was provided by the Amsterdam University Medical center,
630 Amsterdam, the Public Health Services, Amsterdam, and the Dutch Organization for Health Research
631 and Development (ZonMw).

632 **ALSPAC:** Core funding for the Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children (ALSPAC) is
633 provided by the UK Medical Research Council and Wellcome (217065/Z/19/Z) and the University of
634 Bristol. A comprehensive list of grants funding is available on the ALSPAC website
635 (<http://www.bristol.ac.uk/alspac/external/documents/grant-acknowledgements.pdf>).

636 **BiB:** Born in Bradford receives funding from by a joint grant from the UK Medical Research Council
637 (MRC) and UK Economic and Social Science Research Council (ESRC) [MR/N024391/1]; the British
638 Heart Foundation [CS/16/4/32482]; a Wellcome Infrastructure Grant [WT101597MA]; the National
639 Institute for Health Research under its Applied Research Collaboration for Yorkshire and Humber
640 [NIHR200166]; and was supported by UK Research and Innovation for the Healthy Urban Places
641 consortium (grant reference MR/Y022785/1) as part of Population Health Improvement UK (PHI-
642 UK), a national research network which works to transform health and reduce inequalities through
643 change at the population level. The views expressed are those of the author(s), and not necessarily
644 those of the NHS, the NIHR or the Department of Health and Social Care.

645 **DNBC:** The Danish National Birth Cohort was established with a significant grant from the Danish
646 National Research Foundation. Additional support was obtained from the Danish Regional

647 Committees, the Pharmacy Foundation, the Egmont Foundation, the March of Dimes Birth Defects
648 Foundation, the Health Foundation and other minor grants. The DNBC Biobank has been supported
649 by the Novo Nordisk Foundation and the Lundbeck Foundation. Follow-up of mothers and children
650 have been supported by the Danish Medical Research Council (SSVF 0646, 271-08-0839/06-066023,
651 O602-01042B, 0602-02738B), the Lundbeck Foundation (195/04, R100-A9193), The Innovation
652 Fund Denmark 0603-00294B (09-067124), the Nordea Foundation (02-2013-2014), Aarhus Ideas (AU
653 R9-A959-13-S804), University of Copenhagen Strategic Grant (IFSV 2012), and the Danish Council
654 for Independent Research (DFF – 4183-00594 and DFF - 4183-00152).

655 **EDEN:** The EDEN study was supported by Foundation for medical research (FRM), National Agency
656 for Research (ANR), National Institute for Research in Public health (IRESP: TGIR cohorte santé
657 2008 program), French Ministry of Health (DGS), French Ministry of Research, INSERM Bone and
658 Joint Diseases National Research (PRO-A) and Human Nutrition National Research Programs, Paris-
659 Sud University, Nestlé, French National Institute for Population Health Surveillance (InVS), French
660 National Institute for Health Education (INPES), the European Union FP7 programmes (FP7/2007-
661 2013, HELIX, ESCAPE, ENRIECO, Medall projects), Diabetes National Research Program (through
662 a collaboration with the French Association of Diabetic Patients (AFD)), French Agency for
663 Environmental Health Safety (now ANSES), Mutuelle Générale de l'Éducation Nationale a
664 complementary health insurance (MGEN), French national agency for food security, French speaking
665 association for the study of diabetes and metabolism (ALFEDIAM).

666 **Gen R:** The general design of the Generation R Study is made possible by financial support from the
667 Erasmus MC, University Medical Center, Rotterdam, Erasmus University Rotterdam, Netherlands
668 Organization for Health Research and Development (ZonMw), Netherlands Organisation for Scientific
669 Research (NWO), Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport and Ministry of Youth and Families. This
670 project received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme
671 (LIFECYCLE, grant agreement No 733206, 2016; EUCAN-Connect grant agreement No 824989;
672 ATHLETE, grant agreement No 874583; LongITools, grant agreement No 874739). VJ received
673 funding from a Consolidator Grant from the European Research Council (ERC-2014-CoG-648916).

674 **INMA:** This study was funded by grants from the Instituto de Salud Carlos III (Red INMA G03/176)
675 and the Generalitat de Catalunya-CIRIT (1999SGR 00241). INMA-Valencia was funded by Grants
676 from UE (FP7-ENV-2011 cod 282957 and HEALTH.2010.2.4.5-1), Spain: ISCIII (G03/176; FIS-
677 FEDER: PI09/02647, PI11/01007, PI11/02591, PI11/02038, PI13/1944, PI13/2032, PI14/00891,
678 PI14/01687, and PI16/1288; Miguel Servet-FEDER CP11/00178, CP15/00025, and CPII16/00051),
679 and Generalitat Valenciana: FISABIO (UGP 15-230, UGP-15-244, and UGP-15-249). INMA-
680 Gipuzkoa was funded by grants from the Instituto de Salud Carlos III (FISFIS PI06/0867,
681 FISPS09/0009) 0867, Red INMA G03/176) and the Departamento de Salud del Gobierno Vasco
682 (2005111093 and 2009111069) and the Provincial Government of Guipúzcoa (DFG06/004 and
683 FG08/001). INMA-Sabadell was funded by grants from Instituto de Salud Carlos III (Red INMA
684 G03/176; CB06/02/0041; PI041436; PI081151 incl. FEDER funds; PI12/01890 incl. FEDER funds;
685 CP13/00054 incl. FEDER funds; PI15/00118 incl. FEDER funds; CP16/00128 incl. FEDER funds;
686 PI16/00118 incl. FEDER funds; PI16/00261 incl. FEDER funds; PI17/01340 incl. FEDER funds;
687 PI18/00547 incl. FEDER funds), CIBERESP, Generalitat de Catalunya-CIRIT 1999SGR 00241,
688 Generalitat de Catalunya-AGAUR (2009 SGR 501, 2014 SGR 822), Fundació La marató de TV3
689 (090430), Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness (SAF2012-32991 incl. FEDER funds),
690 Agence Nationale de Sécurité Sanitaire de l'Alimentation de l'Environnement et du Travail
691 (1262C0010; EST-2016 RF-21), EU Commission (261357, 308333, 603794 and 634453). Mònica
692 Guxens was funded by a Miguel Servet II fellowship (CPII18/00018) awarded by the Spanish Institute
693 of Health Carlos III. We acknowledge support from the grant CEX2023-0001290-S funded by
694 MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033, and support from the Generalitat de Catalunya through the
695 CERCA Program.

696 **MoBa:** The Norwegian Mother, Father and Child Cohort Study is supported by the Norwegian
697 Ministry of Health and Care Services and the Ministry of Education and Research. We are grateful to
698 all the participating families in Norway who take part in this on-going cohort study. This work was
699 partly supported by the Research Council of Norway through its Centres of Excellence funding
700 scheme, project number 262700. This study includes data from the Norwegian Mother, Father and
701 Child Cohort Study (MoBa) conducted by the Norwegian Institute of Public Health.

702 **NINFEA:** The NINFEA cohort was initially funded by the Compagnia SanPaolo Foundation and the
703 Piedmont Region. It received funding from European projects: CHICOS (FP7 grant number
704 HEALTH-FP7-2009-241604, LifeCycle (H2020 grant number 733206), ATHLETE (H2020 grant
705 number 874583).

706 **RHEA:** The "Rhea" project was financially supported by European projects (EU FP6-2003-Food-3-
707 NewGeneris, EU FP6. STREP Hiwate, EU FP7 NV.2007.1.2.2.2. Project No 211250 Escape, EU FP7-
708 2008-ENV-1.2.1.4 Envirogenomarkers, EU FP7-HEALTH-2009- single stage CHICOS, EU FP7
709 ENV.2008.1.2.1.6. Proposal No 226285 ENRIECO, EU- FP7- HEALTH-2012 Proposal No 308333
710 HELIX) and the Greek Ministry of Health (Program of Prevention of obesity and neurodevelopmental
711 disorders in preschool children, in Heraklion district, Crete, Greece: 2011-2014; "Rhea Plus": Primary
712 Prevention Program of Environmental Risk Factors for Reproductive Health, and Child Health: 2012-
713 15).

714 SW acknowledges receiving the funding by the Generalitat de Catalunya (Agency for Management of
715 University and Research Grants) with a Beatriu de Pinós post-doctoral fellowship (Ref: 2021 BP
716 00058).

717 SS is supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under
718 the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Postdoctoral Fellowship Grant Agreement No. 101109136 (URBANE).

719 The funders had no role in the design and conduct of the study; management, analysis, and
720 interpretation of the data; preparation, review, or approval of the manuscript; and decision to submit
721 the manuscript for publication.

722

723 **Conflicts of Interest**

724 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships
725 that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

726

727 **Acknowledgments**

728 We are grateful to all the participating children, parents, practitioners and researchers in the cohorts
729 who took part in this study.

730 ABCD: We are grateful to all participating hospitals, obstetric clinics, and general practitioners for
731 their assistance in implementing the ABCD study and thank all of the women who participated for
732 their cooperation.

733 ALSPAC: We are extremely grateful to all of the families who took part in ALSPAC, the midwives
734 for their help in recruiting them, and the whole ALSPAC team, which includes interviewers, computer
735 and laboratory technicians, clerical workers, research scientists, volunteers, managers, receptionists
736 and nurses.

737 BiB: BiB is only possible because of the enthusiasm and commitment of the children and parents in
738 BiB. We are grateful to all the participants, health professionals, schools and researchers who have
739 made BiB happen.

740 DNBC: The authors would like to thank the participants, the previous Principal Investigators of DNBC
741 Prof. Jørn Olsen and Prof Anne-Marie Nybo Andersen, the scientific managerial team, and DNBC
742 secretariat for being, establishing, developing and consolidating the Danish National Birth Cohort.

743 EDEN: The authors thank all the participants of the EDEN study and the EDEN mother-child cohort
744 study group, whose members are I. Annesi-Maesano, J.Y. Bernard, M.A. Charles, P. Dargent-Molina,
745 B. de Lauzon-Guillain, P. Ducimetière, M. de Agostini, B. Foliguet, A. Forhan, X. Fritel, A. Germa,
746 V. Goua, R. Hankard, B. Heude, M. Kaminski, B. Larroquey, N. Lelong, J. Lepeule, G. Magnin, L.
747 Marchand, C. Nabet, F. Pierre, R. Slama, M.J. Saurel-Cubizolles, M. Schweitzer, and O.
748 Thiebaugeorges.

749 Gen R: The authors gratefully acknowledge the contribution of participants, research collaborators,
750 general practitioners, hospitals, midwives, and pharmacies in Rotterdam.

751 INMA Gipuzkoa, Sabadell and Valencia: The authors would particularly like to thank all the
752 participants for their generous collaboration. A full roster of the INMA Project Investigators can be
753 found at <https://www.proyectoinma.org/en/inma-project/inma-project-researchers/>.

754 MoBa: We are grateful to all the participating families in Norway who take part in this on-going cohort
755 study.

756 NINFEA: The authors thank all families participating in the NINFEA cohort.

757 RHEA: We are grateful to all the participating families who took part in this cohort study.

758

759 **Data availability**

760 The data that has been used is confidential. Metadata describing the cohorts involved is open access
761 available at the LifeCycle data catalogue at <http://data-catalogue.molgenisccloud.org>

762

763 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

764 **Sarah Warkentin:** Roles/Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing. **Serena Fossati:**
765 Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing - review & editing. **Sandra Marquez:** Methodology,
766 Writing - review & editing, Formal analysis. **Anne-Marie Nybo Andersen:** Writing - review &
767 editing, Funding acquisition. **Sandra Andrusaityte:** Writing - review & editing, Funding
768 acquisition. **Demetris Avraam:** Data curation, Writing - review & editing. **Ferran Ballester:**
769 Writing - review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Tim Cadman:** Writing - review & editing.
770 **Maribel Casas:** Writing - review & editing. **Montserrat de Castro:** Data curation, Writing -
771 review & editing. **Leda Chatzi:** Writing - review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Ahmed**
772 **Elhakeem:** Writing - review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Antonio d'Errico:** Writing - review
773 & editing, Funding acquisition. **Mònica Guxens:** Writing - review & editing, Funding acquisition.
774 **Regina Grazuleviciene:** Writing - review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Jennifer R Harris:**
775 Writing - review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Carmen Iñiguez Hernandez:** Writing - review
776 & editing. Funding acquisition. **Barbara Heude:** Writing - review & editing, Funding acquisition.
777 **Elena Isaevska:** Writing - review & editing. **Vincent WV Jaddoe:** Writing - review & editing,
778 Funding acquisition. **Marianna Karachaliou:** Writing - review & editing. **Aitana Lertxundi:**

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780 **Rosemary RC McEachan:** Writing - review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Johanna L**
781 **Thorbjørnsrud Nader:** Writing - review & editing. **Marie Pedersen:** Conceptualization,
782 Writing - review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Susana Santos:** Writing - review & editing.
783 **Mariska Slofstra:** Writing - review & editing. **Euripides G. Stephanou:** Writing - review &
784 editing. **Morris A Swertz:** Writing - review & editing. **Tanja Vrijkotte:** Writing - review &
785 editing, Funding acquisition. **Tiffany C Yang:** Writing - review & editing. **Mark**
786 **Nieuwenhuijsen:** Conceptualization, Writing - review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Martine**
787 **Vrijheid:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Roles/Writing - original draft, Writing - review &
788 editing, Funding acquisition, Supervision.

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830 air pollution, traffic noise and green space with overweight throughout childhood: The
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Highlights

- We analyzed harmonized data from 10 birth cohorts located in 8 European countries.
- NO₂ exposure did not show robust associations with BMI and overweight/obesity.
- Prenatal PM_{2.5} exposure was associated with 23% higher overweight/obesity risk.
- Postnatal air pollution exposure was not associated with BMI or overweight/obesity.
- High heterogeneity between and associations within specific cohorts were found.

Figure 1. Map of the 10 included cohorts from the EU Child Cohort Network.

Figure 2. Forest plot of associations between pre- and postnatal exposure^a to NO₂ and childhood zBMI and overweight/obesity using two-stage meta-analysis.

ABCD: Amsterdam Born Children and their Development; ALSPAC: Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children; BiB: Born in Bradford; DNBC: Danish National Birth Cohort; EDEN: Etude des Déterminants pré et postnatals précoces du développement et de la santé de l'Enfant; Gen R: Generation R Study; INMA: Infancia y Medio Ambiente; MoBa: Norwegian Mother, Father and Child Cohort Study; NINFEA: Nascita e INFanzia: gli Effetti dell'Ambiente; RHEA: Rhea Mother & Child Cohort Study; zBMI: Body mass index z-score; OR: Odds ratio; CI: Confidence intervals. Prenatal exposure models adjusted for sex, child age (in months), individual-level SES (maternal education), pre-pregnancy BMI, smoking during pregnancy, and area-level SES. Postnatal exposure models were further adjusted for prenatal air pollution exposure. Further adjustments: INMA, NINFEA and EDEN: for city, in Gen R, ABCD and BiB: for ethnicity. I^2 : Test for heterogeneity (%). ^a Values are described as weighted average postnatal air pollution levels in the year before zBMI measurement, in the different age periods. N refers to the number of outcome observations, not number of subjects. **Common effects model: Assumption of one true effect size underlying all studies; Random effects model: effect sizes differ from study to study.**

Figure 3. Forest plot of associations between pre- and postnatal exposure^a to PM_{2.5} and childhood zBMI and overweight/obesity using two-stage meta-analysis.

ABCD: Amsterdam Born Children and their Development; ALSPAC: Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children; BiB: Born in Bradford; DNBC: Danish National Birth Cohort; EDEN: Etude des Déterminants pré et postnatals précoces du développement et de la santé de l'Enfant; Gen R: Generation R Study; INMA: Infancia y Medio Ambiente; MoBa: Norwegian Mother, Father and Child Cohort Study; NINFEA: Nascita e INFanzia: gli Effetti dell'Ambiente; RHEA: Rhea Mother & Child Cohort Study; zBMI: Body mass index z-score; OR: Odds ratio; CI: Confidence intervals. Prenatal exposure models adjusted for sex, child age (in months), individual-level SES (maternal education), pre-pregnancy BMI, smoking during pregnancy, and area-level SES. Postnatal exposure models were further adjusted for prenatal air pollution exposure. Further adjustments: In INMA, NINFEA and EDEN: for city, in Gen R, ABCD and BiB: for ethnicity. I^2 : Test for heterogeneity (%). ^a Values are described as weighted average postnatal air pollution levels in the year before zBMI measurement, in the different age periods. N refers to the number of outcome observations, not number of subjects. **Common effects model: Assumption of one true effect size underlying all studies; Random effects model: effect sizes differ from study to study.**

Figure 4. Pre- and postnatal air pollution exposure^a and childhood overall zBMI and overweight/obesity using two-stage meta-analysis, stratified by age period.

a. NO₂

b. PM_{2.5}

BMI: Body mass index; OR: Odds ratio; CI: Confidence intervals. Prenatal exposure models are adjusted for sex, child age (in months), individual-level SES (maternal education), pre-pregnancy BMI, smoking during pregnancy, and area-level SES. Postnatal exposure models were further adjusted for prenatal air pollution exposure. Further adjustments: In INMA, NINFEA and EDEN: for city, in Gen R, ABCD and BiB: for ethnicity. I²: Test for heterogeneity (%). ^a Values are described as weighted average postnatal air pollution levels in the year before zBMI measurement, in the different age periods. N refers to the number of outcome observations, not number of subjects.

Supplementary materials - content

- Supplementary Text 1.** Cohort-specific ethical approvals _____ page 2
- Supplementary Text 2.** Estimation of weighted averaged air pollution exposure in the LifeCycle project _____ page 3
- Supplementary Text 3.** Cohort-specific description of the area-level SES indicator (deprivation index in tertiles) at pregnancy _____ page 4
- Supplementary Table 1.** Cohort-specific description of anthropometric data source _____ page 5
- Supplementary Table 2.** Population characteristics – full cohorts _____ page 6-7
- Supplementary Table 3.** Associations between pre- and postnatal exposure to NO₂ and childhood zBMI and overweight/obesity using two-stage meta-analysis, using the “leave-one-out approach” - excluding one cohort at a time _____ page 8
- Supplementary Table 4.** Associations between pre- and postnatal exposure to PM_{2.5} and childhood zBMI and overweight/obesity using two-stage meta-analysis, using the “leave-one-out approach” - excluding one cohort at a time _____ page 9
- Supplementary Figure 1.** Flowchart of cohorts and participants for the study of associations between air pollution exposures and zBMI _____ page 10
- Supplementary Figure 2.** Directed Acyclic Graph for prenatal (a) and postnatal (b) air pollution exposure and childhood zBMI _____ page 11
- Supplementary Figure 3.** Correlation plots of prenatal and postnatal air pollutant exposures, by cohort, and available age period _____ page 12
- Supplementary Figure 4.** Associations between NO₂ exposures by period and childhood zBMI and weight status (under-/normal weight vs. overweight/obesity) using two-stage meta-analysis, stratified by individual- and area-level SES _____ page 13
- Supplementary Figure 5.** Associations between PM_{2.5} exposures by period and childhood zBMI and weight status (under-/normal weight vs. overweight/obesity) using two-stage meta-analysis, stratified by individual- and area-level SES _____ page 14
- Supplementary Figure 6.** Associations between air pollution exposures by period and childhood zBMI and weight status (under-/normal weight vs. overweight/obesity) using two-stage meta-analysis, further adjusted by urban characteristics _____ page 15-16

Supplementary Text 1. Cohort-specific ethical approvals.

ABCD: Central Committee on Research involving Human Subjects in the Netherlands, the Medical Ethical Committees of the participating hospitals, and the Registration Committee of the Municipality of Amsterdam.

ALSPAC: ALSPAC Law and Ethics committee and local research ethics committees (NHS Haydock REC: 10/H1010/70).

BiB: Bradford Leeds NHS Research Ethics Committee (07/H1302/112).

DNBC: Danish Data Protection Agency through the joint notification of The Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences at The University of Copenhagen (SUND-2017-09) and the DNBC Steering Committee (2017-23). DNBC cohort is approved by the regional scientific ethical committee under case no. (KF) 01-471/94. DNBC cohort has an additional data protection registration (SUND-2021-6 with case number 514-0631/21-3000).

EDEN: Ethics committee (CCPPRB) of Kremlin Bicêtre and CNIL (Commission Nationale Informatique et Liberté), the French data privacy institution.

Gen R: The general design, all research aims and the specific measurements in the Generation R Study have been approved by the Medical Ethical Committee of the Erasmus Medical Center, Rotterdam. New measurements will only be embedded in the study after approval of the Medical Ethical Committee. The reference numbers of the ethical documents are as follows: phase 1 (fetal period) MEC 198.782/2001/31; phase 2 (0-4 years) MEC 217.595/2002/202; phase 3 (6 and 10 years) MEC-2007-413; MEC-2010-084; MEC-2012-165; phase 4 (13 and 17 years) MEC 2015-749.

INMA: Ethical Committee of the Municipal Institute of Medical Investigation and by the Ethical Committee of the hospitals involved.

MoBa: The establishment of MoBa and initial data collection was based on a license from the Norwegian Data Protection Agency and approval from The Regional Committees for Medical and Health Research Ethics.

NINFEA: Ethical committee of San Giovanni Battista and CTO/CRF/Maria Adelaide Hospital of Turin.

RHEA: Ethical committee of the University Hospital in Heraklion, Greece and the Regional Ethical Review Board in Stockholm, Sweden.

Supplementary Text 2. Estimation of weighted averaged air pollution exposure in the LifeCycle project.

To estimate the postnatal exposure, we considered the weighted averaged air pollution exposure in the year preceding the outcome assessment, which was calculated using the average of exposure weighted for the months in different age-bands, using the equation: $\text{exposure_age-band} = (\text{exposure (age-in-years - 1)} * (12\text{-months}) + \text{exposure_age-in-years} * \text{months}) / 12$.

For example, if the age of the child at follow-up was 45 months, the NO₂ estimate for this specific age-band was identified (variable “no2_4”, which corresponds to the average exposure at age 4 years, i.e. between 36 and 48 months) besides the one corresponding to the year before zBMI measurement - “no2_3” – and these were included in the formula: $\text{NO2}_{2-5} = (\text{no2}_3 * 3 + \text{no2}_4 * 9) / 12$.

Supplementary Text 3. Cohort-specific description of the area-level SES indicator (deprivation index in tertiles) at pregnancy.

ABCD: Status scores - Scores that the Social and Cultural Planning Office (SCP) calculates and that indicate the social status of a neighborhood compared to other neighborhoods in the Netherlands. By social status, we do not mean the prestige or popularity of a neighborhood. The social status of a neighborhood is derived from a number of characteristics of the people who live there: their education, income and position on the labor market. Ref.: The Social and Cultural Planning Office (SCP), Netherland Government. 2002, 2006, 2010, 2014

ALSPAC: Index of Multiple Deprivation (IMD) - Combines information from the seven domains to produce an overall relative measure of deprivation. The domains are combined using the following weights: Income Deprivation (22.5%) Employment Deprivation (22.5%) Education, Skills and Training Deprivation (13.5%) Health Deprivation and Disability (13.5%) Crime (9.3%) Barriers to Housing and Services (9.3%) Living Environment Deprivation (9.3%). Ref.: Ministry of Housing, Communities & Local Government (UK Government). 2015

BiB: Index of Multiple Deprivation (IMD) - Combines information from the seven domains to produce an overall relative measure of deprivation. The domains are combined using the following weights: Income Deprivation (22.5%) Employment Deprivation (22.5%) Education, Skills and Training Deprivation (13.5%) Health Deprivation and Disability (13.5%) Crime (9.3%) Barriers to Housing and Services (9.3%) Living Environment Deprivation (9.3%). Ref.: Ministry of Housing, Communities & Local Government (UK Government). 2015

DNBC: Socioeconomic Status - Based on education level. Ref.: Open data DK. 2016

EDEN: French european deprivation index (EDI) score - Includes overcrowding, no access to a system of central or electric heating, non-owner, unemployment, foreign nationality, no access to a car, unskilled workers - farm workers, household with more than six persons, low level of education, single-parent household. Ref.: Plate-forme méthodologique nationale pour l'étude et la reduction des inégalités sociales en cancérologie (ERISC). 2007

Gen R: Status scores - Scores that the SCP calculates and that indicate the social status of a neighborhood compared to other neighborhoods in the Netherlands. By social status, we do not mean the prestige or popularity of a neighborhood. The social status of a neighborhood is derived from a number of characteristics of the people who live there: their education, income and position on the labor market. Ref.: The Social and Cultural Planning Office (SCP), Netherland Government. 2002, 2006, 2010, 2014

INMA: Urban vulnerability index - Classification according to socioeconomic criteria, includes the whole of 5 socioeconomic indicators: Percentage of unemployed population, percentage of unemployed youth population, percentage of employed persons eventual, percentage of unqualified employed persons and percentage of population without studies. Ref.: Spanish Statistical Office (INE). 2001

MoBa: SES indicator was not provided for the current analysis.

NINFEA: Deprivation Index (Indice di deprivazione) - Built on the basis of 5 variables: Percentage of population with low level of study, percentage of unemployed population, percentage of people with non-home ownership, percentage of one parent family, and population density. Ref.: Agenzia sanitaria e sociale regionale, Emilia-Romagna. 2001

RHEA: Deprivation index - Calculated based on educational level. Ref.: ISGLOBAL based on data from Hellenic Statistical Authority. 2001

Supplementary Table 1. Cohort-specific description of anthropometric data source.

Cohort	Source of Anthropometrics
ABCD	Measured at routine visits in community child health centres (2-48 months), and at ABCD health check visits (5 & 11 years)
ALSPAC	Weight and height measures were obtained from numerous sources from birth to 18 years, including from midwives, health visitors, linkage to child health records, and ALSPAC research clinics. Birth weight/length data were available from obstetric records. Child health records were used for measures up to 4 years. ALSPAC research clinics were used for measures from 4-18 years
BiB	Maternity records; BiB cohort and sub-cohort studies; Healthy Child Programme; GP, National Child Measurement Programme
DNBC	Reported by parents from routine visits at GP (5 & 12 months, and 7 years) and self-reported (11 years)
EDEN	Measured at clinical examinations (birth to 5 years) and collected from GP reports on child's health booklets
Gen R	Measured at routine visits in community child health centres (2-48 months), and at GEN R Research Center (6 & 10 years)
INMA	Measured in a clinical setting
MoBa	Parent-report based on health cards (6 weeks, 3-18 months), and parent-reported (2-8 years)
NINFEA	Child weight and height was reported by parents
RHEA	Measured from trained research assistants at child follow-up visits (9 months, 18 months, 4 years) and collected from pediatrician's reports of child's health booklets (0-5 years)

ABCD: Amsterdam Born Children and their Development; ALSPAC: Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children; BiB: Born in Bradford; DNBC: Danish National Birth Cohort; EDEN: Etude des Déterminants pré et postnatals précoces du développement et de la santé de l'Enfant; Gen R: Generation R Study; INMA: Infancia y Medio Ambiente; MoBa: Norwegian Mother, Father and Child Cohort Study; NINFEA: Nascita e INFanzia: gli Effetti dell'Ambiente; RHEA: Rhea Mother & Child Cohort Study.

Supplementary Table 2. Population characteristics – full cohorts.

	ABCD	ALSPAC	BiB	DNBC	EDEN	Gen R	INMA	MoBa	NINFEA	RHEA
Total N	12395	15645	13858	96825	2002	9901	2270	105311	7645	1458
Area-level deprivation^a - n (%)										
Low	1412 (19.68)	3267 (26.67)	404 (2.92)	4999 (54.49)	707 (38.07)	1154 (13.7)	969 (46.59)	-	900 (37.83)	208 (40.86)
Medium	701 (9.77)	3974 (32.44)	1641 (11.86)	2253 (24.56)	457 (24.61)	1714 (20.4)	850 (40.87)	-	809 (34.01)	172 (33.79)
High	5061 (70.55)	5011 (40.9)	11788 (85.22)	1923 (20.96)	693 (37.32)	5543 (65.9)	261 (12.55)	-	670 (28.16)	129 (25.34)
Missing	5221 (42.12)	3393 (21.69)	25 (0.18)	87650 (90.52)	145 (7.24)	1490 (15.0)	190 (8.37)	105311 (100.0)	5266 (68.88)	949 (65.09)
Maternal education at birth - n (%)										
High	4017 (49.09)	1609 (12.89)	2920 (27.64)	31170 (48.85)	1021 (53.46)	3713 (42.9)	710 (32.63)	62759 (64.22)	4524 (60.47)	382 (28.23)
Medium	2265 (27.68)	8348 (66.87)	1657 (15.69)	24621 (37.8)	745 (39.01)	3980 (46.0)	891 (40.95)	32204 (32.95)	2520 (33.69)	683 (50.48)
Low	1901 (23.23)	2526 (20.24)	5986 (56.67)	9346 (14.35)	144 (7.54)	968 (11.2)	575 (26.42)	2766 (2.83)	437 (5.84)	288 (21.29)
Missing	4212 (33.98)	3162 (20.21)	3295 (23.78)	31688 (32.73)	92 (4.6)	1240 (12.5)	94 (4.14)	7582 (7.2)	164 (2.15)	105 (7.2)
Maternal pre-pregnancy BMI (kg/m²)^b - Median (P5, P95)										
	22.22 (18.52; 30.86)	-	27.69 (20.51; 33.46)	18.19 (14.88; 20.92)	22.11 (18.07; 32.42)	22.66 (18.62; 32.6)	22.55 (18.6; 32.04)	-	21.6 (17.96; 30.04)	23.3 (18.6; 34.4)
Missing	4927 (39.75)	15645 (100.0)	8953 (64.61)	86040 (88.86)	118 (5.86)	2431 (24.55)	57 (2.51)	105311 (100.0)	235 (3.07)	132 (9.05)
Maternal smoking during pregnancy - n(%)										
Yes	866 (10.49)	3663 (30.87)	1885 (16.46)	25021 (26.59)	520 (27.08)	2215 (26.56)	679 (32.16)	24433 (23.41)	639 (8.47)	407 (32.9)
Missing	4143 (33.42)	3779 (24.15)	2405 (17.35)	2727 (2.82)	82 (4.1)	1560 (15.76)	159 (7.0)	921 (0.87)	101 (1.32)	221 (15.16)
Maternal ethnicity										
Western origin	4310 (52.63)	12065 (98.02)	4837 (42.2)	-	1021 (53.46)	5202 (56.77)	2080 (95.37)	-	-	1322 (99.32)
Non-western origin	2744 (33.5)	244 (1.98)	6397 (55.81)	-	745 (39.01)	3479 (37.97)	101 (4.63)	-	-	9 (0.68)
Mixed	1136 (13.87)	0 (0.0)	228 (1.99)	-	144 (7.54)	482 (5.26)	0 (0.0)	-	-	0 (0.0)
Missing	4205 (33.92)	3336 (21.32)	2396 (17.29)	96825 (100.0)	92 (4.6)	738 (7.45)	89 (3.92)	105311 (100.0)	7645 (100.0)	127 (8.71)
Child sex - n (%)										
Male	5933 (51.12)	7706 (51.17)	7153 (51.62)	49644 (51.27)	1000 (52.55)	4937 (50.67)	1099 (51.45)	53865 (51.15)	3456 (50.71)	731 (50.14)
Missing	788 (6.36)	584 (3.73)	1 (0.01)	0 (0.0)	99 (4.95)	157 (1.59)	134 (5.9)	0 (0.0)	830 (10.86)	0 (0.0)
Child age (months) - Median (P5, P95)										
0-2 years	12	12	0	12	20.9	14	14	12	12	14

	(1; 12)	(12; 12)	(0; 23)	(12; 14)	(11.18; 23.97)	(12; 18)	(12; 18)	(1; 16)	(3; 18)	(2; 20)
2-5 years	48	49	52	-	48.3	37	51	36	48	50
	(24; 48)	(31; 49)	(24; 59)	-	(37.09; 59.37)	(24; 47)	(48; 55)	(24; 36)	(48; 48)	(48; 57)
5-9 years	72	99	-	84	95.4	72	93	84	84	-
	(60; 84)	(69; 103)	-	(78; 88)	(66.3; 101)	(68; 89)	(75; 106)	(60; 84)	(74; 94)	-
9-12 years	120	140	-	133	-	116	131	-	121	-
	(120; 120)	(127; 141)	-	(130; 139)	-	(113; 122)	(111; 140)	-	(118; 129)	-

Supplementary Table 3. Associations between pre- and postnatal exposure to NO₂ and childhood zBMI and overweight/obesity using two-stage meta-analysis, using the “leave-one-out approach” - excluding one cohort at a time

	Prenatal NO ₂	Postnatal NO ₂ ^a	Prenatal NO ₂	Postnatal NO ₂ ^a
	β (95%CI), I ²		OR (95%CI), I ²	
Overall effect	0.01 (-0.01; 0.02), 25%	-0.01 (-0.04; 0.02), 74%	1.01 (0.96; 1.07), 39%	1.00 (0.89; 1.12), 73%
Leave one out:				
Cohort ALSPAC	0.01 (-0.01; 0.03), 26.2%	-0.00 (-0.04; 0.03), 75.5%	1.02 (0.97; 1.08), 30.8%	1.03 (0.94; 1.14), 71.9%
Cohort ABCD	0.00 (-0.01; 0.01), 0.0%	-0.02 (-0.05; 0.02), 76.5%	0.99 (0.95; 1.04), 6.0%	0.97 (0.86; 1.10), 73.8%
Cohort BiB	0.01 (-0.01; 0.03), 32.4%	-0.00 (-0.03; 0.03), 74%	1.02 (0.96; 1.08), 45.4%	1.00 (0.87; 1.14), 75.7%
Cohort DNBC	0.01 (-0.01; 0.03), 32.9%	-0.10 (-0.27; 0.07), 89.3%	1.28 (1.04; 1.58), 41.3%	0.83 (0.49; 1.41), 81.8%
Cohort EDEN	0.01 (-0.01; 0.02), 25%	-0.00 (-0.03; 0.03), 72.3%	1.01 (0.95; 1.07), 42.8%	1.02 (0.92; 1.13), 73.7%
Cohort Gen R	0.01 (-0.04; 0.06), 15.1%	-0.02 (-0.05; 0.02), 68.4%	1.00 (0.94; 1.07), 40.4%	0.97 (0.85; 1.1), 73.2%
Cohort INMA	0.01 (-0.01; 0.03), 19.5%	-0.00 (-0.04; 0.03), 71.5%	1.03 (0.97; 1.09), 30.7%	1.02 (0.91; 1.15), 70.5%
Cohort MoBa	0.01 (-0.01; 0.03), 32.2%	-0.01 (-0.05; 0.03), 76.9%	1.02 (0.95; 1.09), 45%	0.99 (0.86; 1.14), 76%
Cohort NINFEA	0.01 (-0.01; 0.03), 24.5%	-0.01 (-0.05; 0.02), 77.1%	1.02 (0.95; 1.09), 45.7%	0.97 (0.86; 1.11), 74.8%
Cohort RHEA	0.01 (-0.01; 0.02), 32.2%	-0.00 (-0.04; 0.03), 74.5%	1.01 (0.96; 1.07), 42.1%	1.02 (0.92; 1.13), 69%

ABCD: Amsterdam Born Children and their Development; ALSPAC: Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children; BiB: Born in Bradford; DNBC: Danish National Birth Cohort; EDEN: Etude des Déterminants pré et postnatals précoces du développement et de la santé de l'Enfant; Gen R: Generation R Study; INMA: Infancia y Medio Ambiente; MoBa: Norwegian Mother, Father and Child Cohort Study; NINFEA: Nascita e INFanzia: gli Effetti dell'Ambiente; RHEA: Rhea Mother & Child Cohort Study; OR: Odds ratio; CI: Confidence intervals. Prenatal exposure models adjusted for sex, child age (in months), individual-level SES (maternal education), pre-pregnancy BMI, smoking during pregnancy, and area-level SES. Postnatal exposure models were further adjusted for prenatal air pollution exposure. Further adjustments: INMA, NINFEA and EDEN: for city, in Gen R, ABCD and BiB: for ethnicity. I²: Test for heterogeneity (%). ^a Values are described as weighted average postnatal air pollution levels in the year before zBMI measurement, in the different age periods.

Supplementary Table 4. Associations between pre- and postnatal exposure to PM_{2.5} and childhood zBMI and overweight/obesity using two-stage meta-analysis, using the “leave-one-out approach” - excluding one cohort at a time

	Prenatal PM_{2.5}	Postnatal PM_{2.5}^a	Prenatal PM_{2.5}	Postnatal PM_{2.5}^a
	β (95%CI), I²		OR (95%CI), I²	
Overall effect	0.04 (-0.03; 0.10), 44%	-0.10 (-0.26; 0.05), 89%	1.23 (1.01; 1.51), 43%	0.86 (0.55; 1.35), 80%
Leave one out:				
Cohort ALSPAC	0.05 (-0.01; 0.11), 21.6%	-0.08 (-0.25; 0.08), 89.3%	1.24 (1.01; 1.54), 49.2%	0.96 (0.64; 1.46), 79.1%
Cohort ABCD	0.02 (-0.05; 0.10), 47.4%	-0.12 (-0.29; 0.06), 89.9%	1.20 (0.97; 1.49), 46%	0.80 (0.48; 1.35), 81.9%
Cohort BiB	0.05 (-0.01; 0.11), 38.1%	-0.10 (-0.27; 0.07), 89.3%	1.28 (1.04; 1.58), 41.3%	0.83 (0.49; 1.41), 81.8%
Cohort DNBC	0.03 (-0.05; 0.11), 50.2%	-0.13 (-0.30; 0.04), 90%	1.28 (1.02; 1.59), 45.9%	0.80 (0.48; 1.33), 81.8%
Cohort EDEN	0.03 (-0.04; 0.10), 50.3%	-0.10 (-0.26; 0.07), 89.9%	1.21 (0.97; 1.49), 46.2%	0.85 (0.52; 1.41), 82%
Cohort Gen R	0.01 (-0.04; 0.06), 15.1%	-0.14 (-0.28; -0.00), 79.7%	1.11 (0.98; 1.28), 8.6%	0.78 (0.50; 1.23), 76.4%
Cohort INMA	0.03 (-0.04; 0.10), 50.3%	-0.05 (-0.19; 0.08), 84.8%	1.23 (0.99; 1.54), 49.5%	1.05 (0.76; 1.47), 70.4%
Cohort MoBa	0.04 (-0.04; 0.12), 47.1%	-0.12 (-0.30; 0.05), 90.1%	1.29 (1.02; 1.62), 43.4%	0.81 (0.48; 1.38), 82.1%
Cohort NINFEA	0.03 (-0.05; 0.12), 49%	-0.13 (-0.30; 0.04), 90%	1.27 (1.00; 1.63), 46%	0.79 (0.48; 1.31), 81.4%
Cohort RHEA	0.03 (-0.03; 0.10), 50.2%	-0.07 (-0.21; 0.07), 88.9%	1.20 (0.98; 1.47), 40.4%	0.98 (0.67; 1.43), 77.2%

ABCD: Amsterdam Born Children and their Development; ALSPAC: Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children; BiB: Born in Bradford; DNBC: Danish National Birth Cohort; EDEN: Etude des Déterminants pré et postnatals précoces du développement et de la santé de l’Enfant; Gen R: Generation R Study; INMA: Infancia y Medio Ambiente; MoBa: Norwegian Mother, Father and Child Cohort Study; NINFEA: Nascita e INFanzia: gli Effetti dell’Ambiente; RHEA: Rhea Mother & Child Cohort Study; OR: Odds ratio; CI: Confidence intervals. Prenatal exposure models adjusted for sex, child age (in months), individual-level SES (maternal education), pre-pregnancy BMI, smoking during pregnancy, and area-level SES. Postnatal exposure models were further adjusted for prenatal air pollution exposure. Further adjustments: INMA, NINFEA and EDEN: for city, in Gen R, ABCD and BiB: for ethnicity. I²: Test for heterogeneity (%). ^a Values are described as weighted average postnatal air pollution levels in the year before zBMI measurement, in the different age periods.

Supplementary Figure 1. Flowchart of cohorts and participants for the study of associations between air pollution exposures and zBMI.

Supplementary Figure 2. Directed Acyclic Graph for prenatal (a) and postnatal (b) air pollution exposure and childhood zBMI.

(a)

(b)

Supplementary Figure 3. Correlation plots of prenatal and postnatal air pollutant exposures, by cohort, and available age period*.

*For BiB and RHEA, postnatal age period available until 2-5 years; for EDEN and MoBa: 5-9 years; for Gen R and NINFEA: 9-11 years; for ABCD, ALSPAC, DNBC and INMA: 9-12 years.

Supplementary Figure 4. Associations between NO₂ exposures by period and childhood zBMI and weight status (under-/normal weight vs. overweight/obesity) using two-stage meta-analysis, stratified by individual- and area-level SES.

BMI: Body mass index; OR: Odds ratio; CI: Confidence intervals; SES: Socioeconomic status; T: Tertile. Prenatal exposure models adjusted for sex, child age (in months), individual-level SES (maternal education), pre-pregnancy BMI, smoking during pregnancy, and area-level SES, however removing each time the specific variable used for stratification. Postnatal exposure models were further adjusted for prenatal air pollution exposure. Further adjustments: In INMA, NINFEA and EDEN: for city, in Gen R, ABCD and BiB: for ethnicity. I²: Test for heterogeneity (%). Postnatal exposure levels are described as weighted average air pollution levels in the year before zBMI measurement.

Supplementary Figure 5. Associations between PM_{2.5} exposures by period and childhood zBMI and weight status (under-/normal weight vs. overweight/obesity) using two-stage meta-analysis, stratified by individual- and area-level SES.

BMI: Body mass index; OR: Odds ratio; CI: Confidence intervals; SES: Socioeconomic status; T: Tertile. Prenatal exposure models adjusted for sex, child age (in months), individual-level SES (maternal education), pre-pregnancy BMI, smoking during pregnancy, and area-level SES, however removing each time the specific variable used for stratification. Postnatal exposure models were further adjusted for prenatal air pollution exposure. Further adjustments: In INMA, NINFEA and EDEN: for city, in Gen R, ABCD and BiB: for ethnicity. I²: Test for heterogeneity (%). Postnatal exposure levels are described as weighted average air pollution levels in the year before zBMI measurement.

Supplementary Figure 6. Associations between air pollution exposures by period and childhood zBMI and weight status (under-/normal weight vs. overweight/obesity) using two-stage meta-analysis, further adjusted by urban characteristics.

a. NO₂

